

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, Mukka, Mangalore – 574 146, Phone :0824-2477456

(State Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013 empowered to award degrees under Section 22 of UGC Act of UGC, New Delhi, & Member of Association of Indian Universities, New Delhi)

Web :www.srinivasuniversity.ac.in, Email: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Program Syllabus

for

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Programme Core (Based on UGC –LOCF)

The realities have changed, the context has changed, the practice is changing and therefore the approach of learning has to alongside change.

Board of Studies in Arts

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

(2021 ONWARDS)

R.19 Semester wise Subjects details

SEMESTER I: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ01	Fundamentals of Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ02	Reporting (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ03 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Early Childhood Development	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ03 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Principles of Management									
4	21BAJ04	Field Practicum – I Media Visit (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ05	Fundamentals of Communication I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ06 K	Kannada I (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ06 H	Hindi I (AECC)									
	21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I (AECC)									
	21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I (AECC)									
7	21BAJ07	Digital Proficiency I (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ08	Health & Wellness (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ09	Basics of Nutrition (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ10	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total				300				750	28

*DSC- Discipline

*DSC- Discipline Elective

*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses

AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER II: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ11	Editing (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ12	Radio Broadcasting	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ13 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Human Resource Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ13 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Youth Development through Social Work									
4	21BAJ14	Field Practicum – II Event Reporting (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ15	Fundamentals of Communication II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ16 K	Kannada II (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ16 H	Hindi II (AECC)									
	21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II (AECC)									
	21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II (AECC)									
7	21BAJ17	Digital Proficiency II (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ18	NSS (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ19	Life Skills (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ20	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
		Total					320			750	28

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SEMESTER III: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ21	Print Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ22	Advertisement (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ23 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Disaster Management	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ23 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Management Information system									
4	21BAJ24	Field Practicum – III Media Advertisement (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ25	Functional English-I (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ26 K	Kannada III (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
	21BAJ26 H	Hindi III (AECC)									
	21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III (AECC)									
	21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III (AECC)									
7	21BAJ27	Cyber Crime and Security (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ28	Games (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ29	Waste Management (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2
10	21BAJ30	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-
Total						320				750	28

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*OE -open Elective

*SEC – Skilled Enhancement Courses

AECC- Ability Enhancement Compulsory Course

SEMESTER IV: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Internal			External	Total		
1	21BAJ31	Electronic Journalism (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
2	21BAJ32	New Media Technology (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
3	21BAJ33 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Social Work Research	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4	
	21BAJ33 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) E- Business										
4	21BAJ34	Field Practicum – IV Anchoring (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4	
5	21BAJ35	Functional English-II (E) (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3	
6	21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3	
	21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV (AECC)										
	21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV (AECC)										
	21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV (AECC)										
7	21BAJ37	Entrepreneurship Start up (SEC)	-	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2	
8	21BAJ38	Yoga (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2	
9	21BAJ39	Indian Constitution (SEC)	20	-	-	20	-	50	-	50	2	
10	21BAJ40	CommunicativeKannada	-	-	-	-	20	-	-	-	-	
Total						320				750	28	

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SEMESTER V: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours			Total Hrs	Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)			Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ41	Public Relation (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ42	Film Production (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ43 (A)	Open Elective-1 (OE) Health care	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
	21BAJ43 (B)	Open Elective-2 (OE) Entrepreneur ship Development									
4	21BAJ44	Field Practicum – V Documentary film (DSC)	-	8	32	40	-	50	50	100	4
5	21BAJ45	Auditing techniques (AECC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
6	21BAJ46	Excel and SPSS	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	3
7	21BAJ47	Television Production (SEC)	-			20	-	50	-	50	2
8	21BAJ48	Music/Dance (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
9	21BAJ49	Street Play (SEC)	20			20	-	50	-	50	2
Total						300				750	28

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SEMESTER VI: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ51	Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce (SEC)	-	8	320	320	-	Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300	External Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300 Viva-Voce exam = 150	750	28

SEMESTER VII: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ61	Communication Research Methods and Application (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ62	Media Law and Ethics (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ63	Magazine and Photo Journalism(DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BAJ64	Project – TV & Radio			200 HRS	200 HRS		350	100	450	16

EMESTER VIII: Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

Sl. No.	Code	Title of Course	Teaching hours				Practical sessions/Self/Study (S)	Exam			Credits
			Lecture (L)	Tutorial	Practical (P)	Total Hrs		Internal	External	Total	
1	21BAJ71	Development Communication (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
2	21BAJ72	Marketing Communication (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
3	21BAJ73	Case Studies (DSC)	40	-	-	40	-	50	50	100	4
4	21BAJ74	Dissertation			200 HRS	200 HRS		350	100	450	16

20. Examination Pattern:

Theory Papers: **Internal Assessment Marks:**

Outline for continuous assessment activities for C1 and C2 are as follows:

Activities	C1	C2	Total Marks
Session Test	-	20	20
Seminars/Presentations/Activity	10		10
Case study /Assignment / Project work etc.		15	15
Attendance		5	5
Total	10 marks	40 marks	50 Marks

At the end of each semester, examinations will be conducted for all the papers to be covered in that semester and evaluation will be done for 50 marks each. The timings of the examination will be followed as per academic calendar.

21 Pattern of Question Paper in End Semester Examination:

The question paper pattern in each Semester Exam for 50 marks consists of Objective type questions 6 questions all to answer (6 marks), Very short answer three questions out of four questions (6 marks) Seven marks questions 4 out of 5 questions (28 marks) , and one long essay of 10 marks out of two (10 marks).

No. of	Type	Question/Marks	Total Marks
6 out of 6	Objective type	6 x 1 = 06	06
3 out of 4	Very short	3 x 2= 06	06
4 out of 5	Short essay	4 x 7 = 28	28
1 out of 2	Long essay	1 x 10 =10	10
Total Semester Marks			50

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

SEMESTER I

21BAJ01: Fundamentals of Journalism

Subject Code	21BAJ01	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2hrs

Course Objectives

To understand the importance, functions & scope of communication and media.

To describe the growth and development of communication and media.

To understand the periodic changes in the media.

Course Outcomes

CO1. Learners will know the importance, functions & scope of communication.

CO2. Able to understand the media and changes.

CO3. Able to practice the technology in media.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Introduction to Journalism: Nature, Scope and definition of journalism,

Meaning of Journalism, Meaning of craft, As a profession, as an industry.

Role and responsibilities of a Journalist, Meaning of Mass Media.

Theories of the Press Communication, Public opinion and democracy.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation

MODULE –II

8 HRS

Journalist – Their role and responsibilities

Indian Constitution and freedom of press, Careers in Journalism and mass media. Professional organisations in Media

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE –III

8 HRS

A brief Review of the Evolution of Indian Press, with reference to J A Hickey, Raja Ram Mohan Roy, James Silk Buckingham, M K Gandhi, S. Sadanand and B. G. Horniman, Kannada Journalism: Origin, Growth and development.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE –IV

8 HRS

News: Meaning & definition, Sources and elements of news
Characteristics of news. Mass Communication: Concept & Characteristics. Different styles of news writing in Newspaper. News Agencies, Photo Journalism. Cartoons.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE –V

8 HRS

Printing technology and production methods, Photography: Camera
Lens, Depth of Field. Page design, Cartoon, Color Techniques.

Pedagogy: PPT, Group Discussion, Video clips, Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

References

B N Ahuja: History of Indian Press – Growth of Newspapers in India, Surjeet Publications, Delhi, 2009

D S Mehta: Mass Communication and Journalism in India, Aliied Publishers Pvt Ltd., Mumbai, 2006

William L. Rivers: The Mass Media: Reporting Writing Editing, Harper & Row, 1975

F. Fraser Bond: An Introduction to Journalism, The Macmillan Company, 1954

Nadig Krishnamurthy: Indian Journalism, Prasaranga, Mysore University, Mysore, 1966

Rangaswami Parthasarathy: Journalism in India, Sterling Publications Pvt. Ltd., 1997

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SEMESTER I 21BAJ02 Reporting

Subject Code	21BAJ02	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Information dissemination across traditional and digital publication platforms demands accuracy.
2. Introduce the fairness that act as the hallmark of writing professionals.
3. Students will understand how writing is delivered across various verticals.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will identify the dissemination across traditional and digital publication platforms.

CO2. Explain the demands accuracy and fairness that act as the hallmark of writing professionals.

CO3. Choose to write the small stories independently.

Course content

MODULE – I

8 HRS

Introduction: Sociology- Definition

News – definitions, News values

Elements of news, Sources of news

Structure of a news story – lead, types of leads- body.

Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion

MODULE -II

Reporting for print

Radio

Television and new media, Package stories for TV

Attributes of a reporter, Media convergence.

Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion

8 HRS

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Types of news stories
Crime Stories
Court – legislature – politics
Culture – environment, Sports
Investigative, Reporting and development reporting.
Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Press conferences,
Interviews, Types and techniques of Interview
Press release, Reporting for news agencies.
Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group
Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE - V

8 HRS

New trends in reporting
Mobile journalism
Citizen journalism.
Pedagogy: Chalk and talk, PPT, and Group Discussion

References

- Abraham, M. F., (2006). *Contemporary Sociology: An Introduction to Concepts and Theory*. Barnas, Frank. (2017). *Broadcast news writing, reporting and producing*. New York:Routledge.
- James G. Stovall (2014). *Writing for the Mass Media*. Indianapolis: Pearson Educations.
- Mencher, Melvin. (2006). *Melvin Mencher's news reporting and writing*. Boston: McGraw- Hill
- Phillips, Angela. (2007). *Good Writing for Journalists*. New Delhi: Sage
- Rajan, Nalini. (2007). *21st Century Journalism in India*. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
- Sharma, Diwakar. (2005). *Modern journalism: Reporting and writing*. New Delhi: Deep &Deep.
- Shrivastava, K.M. (2015). *News reporting and editing*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.
- Steen, Rob. (2008). *Sports journalism*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Strentz Herbert. (2002). *News reporting and news sources*. New Delhi: Prentice Hall.

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SEMESTER I

21BAJ03(A) EARLY CHILDHOOD DEVELOPMENT

Subject Code	21BAJ03(A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To understand how children develop and the psychological significance of development.
2. To understand the fundamental facts about principles of development.
3. To know how emotions play an important role in children 's lives.
4. To know the contributions of Play.

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to relate the psychological significance of development

CO2. Able to Assess the principles of development.

CO3. Able to examine an important role in children 's lives.

Course content

MODULE – I

8 HRS

Growth and Development, Concept of Growth and Development

Factors influencing Development, Principles of Development

Hazards in Physical Development

Pedagogy: PPT, Group Discussion, Video clips, Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Emotional Development

Characteristic features of Children 's Emotions

Effect of emotions on Children 's Personal and Social adjustments

Hazards in Emotional Development

Causes for behaviour problems in children

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Play Development - Play – Meaning and Definition

Characteristics of Children 's Play

Contributions of play to Children 's Personality Development.

Hazards in play Development

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Nurturing Children- Needs of children –Significance, security, acceptance, love, praise and discipline

Art of effective parenting, Components of child- friendly schools

Life skills for effective molding of Behaviour.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - V

8 HRS

Nutrition- Nutritional requirements of infants, pre-school children pregnancy and lactation, modification of normal diets

A brief study of common diseases in childhood (fever, cough, cold, polio, diphtheria, measles, diarrhoea, dysentery, tetanus, eye and ear infection.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

Bettie, B. Young. Keeping your Children Safe: A Practical Guide for Parents. Bombay: St. Paul Publications, 1994.

D'Souza, Barnalu. Walking with Vulnerable Children. Mumbai: Don Bosco Research, Documentation & Training Centre, 2006.

Ginott, Haim, G. between Parent and Child. New York: Avon Books, 1956.

Green, Christaphi. Toddler Taming: A Parent 's Guide to the First Four Years. London: Vermillion, 1992.

Guptha, Sangeetha. The Joy of Parenting. New Delhi: Unicorn Books Pvt. Ltd, 2003.

Hurlock, Elizabeth. Child Development. Sydney: McGraw Hill, 1978.

Hurlock, S B. Child Growth and Psychology. New Delhi: Tata McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd, 1990.

Lakshamma, T. Professional Training in Social Work. New Delhi: Discovery Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., 2010.

Meyers, G. C. Becoming a Modern Parent. New Delhi: Infinity Books, 2002.

SEMESTER 1

21BAJ03 (B) PRINCIPALS OF MANAGEMENT

Subject Code	21BAJ03 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Understand, and present management principles, processes and procedures.
2. Knowledge on the Principles of Management will enable the student manager and/ or employee.
3. Gain valuable insight into the workings of business and other organizations.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will able to Apply present management principles, processes and procedures.

CO2. Able to distinguish the problems and situations from both the text and student experience.

CO3. Magnify and modify the situation in Managing the employer.

Course content

MODULE I

Introduction to Management: Definition, Meaning

8 HRS

Nature, Features, Objectives, Functions

Managerial, Evolution of Management Thought-

Contribution of Fredrick Taylor, Contribution of Henry Fayol.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE II

8 HRS

Planning: Nature, and Importance.

Process, Types of Plans. Decision making, Meaning, significance, scientific decision-making process, Guidelines for effective decision making. Communication Process.

Types, Barriers of communication, Essentials of Effective communication.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE III

8 HRS

Organizing: Principles of organizing

Types of Organization structure, Line organization,
Functional Organization, Line and staff organization.

Delegation of authority- Barriers to effective delegation

Guidelines for making effective delegation.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE IV

8 HRS

Staffing: Concept of Staffing

Need, Recruitment- Factors, Sources of Recruitment, Techniques. Selection- Scientific Selection Process.

Training and Development- Importance, Methods.

Performance Appraisal-Objectives, Methods.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE V

Direction And Control: Meaning, Elements.

8 HRS

Controlling- Meaning, Importance, Techniques.

Motivation- Concept, Importance,

Theories - Maslow's Need Hierarchy theory- Herzberg's

Hygiene theory- McGregor's Theory X and Y.

Leadership Qualities- Leadership Styles.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference

Principles of Management: C.B. Gupta

Management concepts and Practice: B.P Singh and T.N. Chabra

Principles of Management: H Koontz and C.O. Donnel

Management: V.S.P. Rao and V. Harikrishna

Principles of Management: L.M. Prasad

Principles of Management: Tripathi and Reddy

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SEMESTER I

21BAJ04 – Field Practicum – 1

Subject Code	21BAJ04	IA Marks	-
Total Contact Hours	16 Hours per week (25 Field work Visits)	Summative Assessment Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	--	Total = 100 Marks	100
Credits	04		

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of field practicum, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation

Course Outcome

CO1. To Utilize the concept to field practicum education to develop self-awareness

CO2. Able to develop skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions.

CO3. Able to plan and interpret programmes and projects.

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SEMESTER I

21BAJ05 -FUNDAMENTALS OF COMMUNICATION I

Subject Code	21BAJ05	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. The objective of this course is to enhance the student's communication skills by giving adequate exposure in listening
2. Improve speaking, reading and writing skills and the related sub-skills.
3. The course is a step towards preparing the learners to face situations with confidence and to seek employment in the modern globalized world.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will heighten their awareness of correct usage of English grammar in writing and speaking.

CO2. Assume their speaking ability in English both in terms of fluency

CO3. Evaluate the comprehensibility in their performance.

Course content

MODULE I

Basics of English Grammar **8HRS**

Parts of speech – noun, pronoun, verbs, adjectives, adverb, prepositions, conjunction, interjections.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE II

Basics of English Grammar II **8HRS**

Sentences- types and construction of sentences, Articles – a, an and the, Phrases clauses and idioms, Wh- questions and question tags.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE III

Literature; **8HRS**

The Tyger -William Blake

My grandmother's House – Kamala Das

I wandered lonely as a cloud – William Wordsworth

The road not taken – Robert Frost

Sonnet 116 – William Shakespeare

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE IV

Business Communication

8HRS

Introduction, Types of communication,

Barriers to Communication and steps to overcome them,

Importance of effective communication, Cultural differences and Diversity in Communication, body language in professional work environment,

Professional etiquette rules every person should follow.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE V

Writing skills

8HRS

Business writing- minutes, memos

notices, pressie writing, project reports

Informal letters, job applications with resume, Comprehension.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference

High School Wren and Martin English Grammar and Composition

A practical English grammar- A.J Thomson – Oxford University Press

A handbook of English grammar and usage- d thakur – Bharathi Bhawan Publications

Writing reports – Seely, John

Business Communication: A practice-oriented approach – Shalini Kalia

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SEMESTER I

21BAJ06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ06 K	Kannada I
21BAJ06 H	Hindi I
21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I
21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BAJ06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

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SEMESTER I 21BAJ07 –Digital Proficiency -1

Subject Code	21BAJ07	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To understand the importance of technology in social work
2. To practice the digital skills.
3. Using of various mobile apps.

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to identify the importance of digital skills.

CO2. Can apply digital skills in social work Practice.

CO3. To Assess the programs in Computers

Course content

MODULE –I

5 HRS

Introduction, Generation of computers, Classification of computers, Application of computers.

Introduction, Central Processing unit, main memory unit, interconnection of units, communication between various units of a computer system.

Input devices: Introduction, Types of input devices.

Introduction to Microsoft Office, Microsoft Word, Microsoft PowerPoint, Introduction to Libre office. Introduction to a word processor: create and save a document.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical

Module -II

3 HRS

Edit and format text: text style (B, I, U), font type, font size, text colour, alignment of text. Format paragraphs with line and/or paragraph spacing. Add headers and footers, numbering pages, grammar and spell check utilities, subscript and superscript, insert symbols, use print preview, and print a document.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

Module -III

2 HRS

Insert pictures, change the page setting, add bullets and numbering, borders and shading, and insert tables – insert/delete rows and columns, merge and split cells.

Use auto-format, track changes, review comments, use of drawing tools, shapes and mathematical symbols.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

Module -IV

5 HRS

Presentation tool: understand the concept of slide shows, basic elements of a slide, different types of slide layouts create and save a presentation, and learn about the different views of a slide set – normal view, slide sorter view and hand-outs.

Edit and format a slide: add titles, subtitles, text, background, and watermark, headers and footers, and slide numbers.

Insert pictures from files, create animations, add sound effects, and rehearse timings. Spreadsheets: concept of a worksheet and a workbook, create and save a worksheet.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

Module -V

5 HRS

Working with a spreadsheet: enter numbers, text, date/time, series using auto fill; edit and format a worksheet including changing the colour, size, font, alignment of text; insert and delete cells, rows and columns. Enter a formula using the operators (+, -, *, /), refer to cells, and print a worksheet.

Use simple statistical functions: SUM (), AVERAGE (), MAX (), MIN (), IF () (without compound statements); embed charts of various types: line, pie, scatter, bar and area in a worksheet.

Introduction to Scratch. Drag and drop commands, creating simple scripts, repeating blocks of commands.

Discuss x-y plane, create report. Create a script to draw diagrams using the pen feature.

Internet and Communication: Effective usage of Internet: Email–Gmail, Outlook, Usage of social media for Social Campaign: Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn, Instagram, Pinterest.

Effective Usage of Digital Technology during Pandemic Situation.

Digital Social Work Zoom, Google Meet, Club House, Microsoft Meet.

Introducing canva – Poster making, Flier, PPT, Effective Usage of Digital Technology during Pandemic Situation.

Digital Social Work Zoom, Google Meet, Club House, Microsoft Meet.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Lab and practical.

References

Laurelet.al., (2019), Teaching Social Work with Digital Technology, CSWE Press

Godfred Boahen (2020), *COVID-19: Using Digital Technology in Relationship-Based Practice to Bridge the Gap in Social Distancing*, Social care institute for excellence, <https://www.scie.org.uk/social-work/digital-capabilities/blogs/covid-digital-echnology>

John Hughes (2020), *Zoom vs Microsoft Teams vs Google Meet: Top Video Conferencing Apps Compared*, codinwp, <https://www.codeinwp.com/blog/zoom-vs-microsoft-teams-vs-google-meet/>

Frederic G. (2019), Social Work Education in a Digital World: Technology Standards for Education and Practice, *Journal of Social Work Education*, 55(2):1-13

Digital Reference

Digital Technology and Social Work: <https://www.basw.co.uk/digital-technology-and-social-work-webinar-4-Ways-to-Use-Digital-Tools-to-Engage-Clients> <https://www.socialwork-career.com/2014/02/4-ways-to-use-digital-tools-to-engage-clients.html>

Hong Zhu & Synnøve T (2021) Andersen Digital competence in social work practice and education: experiences from Norway: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/2156857X.2021.1899967>

Digital capabilities for social workers: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ft6kW-GMmIE>
Social work practice with digital communication technologies: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Oja8V5GcoTk>

Digital technologies for social inclusion: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/dspd/2021/02/digital-technologies-for-social-inclusion-2/>

Digital Capabilities for Social Workers: <https://www.scie.org.uk/social-work/digital-capabilities/resources/social-workers>.

A Review of the New Standards for Technology in Social Work Practice <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gj8hjvikp44>

Future is Bright for AI and Social Work <https://www.cais.usc.edu/news/future-is-bright-for-ai-and-social-work>

Make Time for What Matters Part 2: Using Technology to Improve Efficiency and Developing Strong Relationships <https://schoolsocialwork.net/make-time-for-what-matters-part-2-using-technology-to-improve-efficiency-and-developing-strong-relationships/>

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

SEMESTER I 21BAJ08 –Health and Wellness

Subject Code	21BAJ08	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours Campus network Based	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To introduce the fundamental concepts of physical education, health and wellness.
2. To provide a general understanding on nutrition, first aid and stress management.
3. To familiarize the students regarding yoga and other activities for developing wellness. As well as to create awareness regarding hypo-kinetic diseases, and various measures of health and wellness assessment.

Course Outcome

CO1. Analyse the importance of Health and wellness

CO2. Defend individual groups and community to maintain sound health.

CO3. Simplify lifestyle and other diseases

Course content

Campus network Based

MODULE –I

3HRS

Introduction to Health and Wellness

Defining Health and Wellness, Personal Health Assessment, Factors Contributing to Health Behavior Change. Dimensions of health and wellness

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes.

MODULE –II

4HRS

Relationship between lifestyle and health. Physiological and psychological bases of stress. Key components of fitness.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes

MODULE -III

4HRS

Ways to achieve and maintain ideal body composition Influential Factors for Ideal Body Composition

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes

MODULE –IV

Risk factors and risk reduction strategies associated with the major communicable and non-communicable disease and threats to health and well-being. **4HRS**

Influences of psycho-social, economic, physical, hereditary, race, gender, and culture on health. Bio-psycho-social model

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes

MODULE –V

5HRS

Lifestyle Disease and its Management, Lifestyle/Hypo-kinetic Diseases and its Management-Diabetes-Hypertension - Obesity - Osteoporosis - CHD – Back pain Health related Physical Fitness and Assessment Body mass Index/ Skin fold Measurement, BMR, Pulse Rate, Blood Pressure, Health Related Physical Fitness Test.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion and participation in programmes.

References

AAPHERD. “Health Related Physical Fitness Test Manual”. 1980 Published by Association drive Reston Virginia

ACSM Fitness Book, Leisure Press Campaign, Illinois, 1996, Leisure Press, Canada
<http://www.pitt.edu/~gsphome>.

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

SEMESTER I 21BAJ09 BASICS OF NUTRITION

Subject Code	21BAJ09	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	---
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. Know the role of food in health
2. Obtain knowledge on different food groups, their composition and role in diet
3. Understand different methods of processing, cooking, the basic structure of human digestive system.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will Experiment and become familiar with the terms of nutrition.

CO2. Discover the idea on the concept of health

CO3. Students will be deciding the significance of emotional intelligence in their day-to-day activities.

Course Content

MODULE I

4HRS

Definition of food- food as a source of nutrients; Definition of Health; Dimension of Health – physical, social and mental health

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Practical sessions and competitions.

MODULE II

Food – energy giving, body building and protective; Functions of food- physiological, **3HRS** psychological and social; Food pyramid.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Practical sessions and competitions.

MODULE III

4 HRS

Definition of Nutrition; Group of Nutrients – micro and macro nutrients; Diet – balanced diet, metabolism, malnutrition, under nutrition, over nutrition; Is water a nutrient; Deficiency diseases; Relation between food and nutrition, health and diseases.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE IV

4 HRS

Carbohydrates- definition and classification; sources and daily requirements; Lipids – definition, and classification; Proteins – definition and classification: sources and daily requirements; Amino acids – classification, types and functions; Fat – classification and functions.

Food and their nutrient contents; Nutrients present in cereals, millets, pulses nuts and oil seeds, fruits and vegetables, milk and milk products, flesh food, eggs, spices and salt.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE V

Cooking: beneficial and adverse effects of cooking

5 HRS

Different methods of cooking- dry, moist, frying and micro wave cooking- advantage and disadvantage and the effect of various methods of cooking on foods, solar cooking.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion, cooking practices and competitions

References

Passmore R. and Davidson S. (1986) Human nutrition and Dietetics. Liming stone publishers.

Shil's M.E., Alfon J.A., Shike M (1994), Modern nutrition in health and diseases eighth edition.

Shakuntala Manay N - Food Facts and Principles, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi – 110002, 2005.

Srilakshmi B- Food Science, 5th Edition, New Age International Publishers, New Delhi – 110002, 2011.

Mudambi SR and Rajagopal, MV. Fundamentals of Foods and Nutrition, New Age International (P) Ltd., Publishers, 4th edn, New Delhi. 2008.

Manay SN and Shadaksharaswamy M. Foods: Facts and Principles, New Age International (P) Ltd. New Delhi. 2010.

Goleman D (1995) Emotional intelligence: why it can matter more than IQ. Bantam Books

Goleman D (2006) Social intelligence: the new science of social relationships. Bantam Books

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

SEMESTER I

21BAJ10 COMMUNICATIVE KANNADA (Only for Non-Kannadigas)

Subject Code	21BAJ10	IA Marks	-
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	---
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	-
Credits	--	Exam Hours	--

Pedagogy: Communication, Translations and Group discussions.

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SECOND SEMESTER

21BAJ11 Editing

Subject Code	21BAJ11	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. The course elucidates on eye for detail while editing and proofing of stories/ wire service copies, understanding design elements, layouts, and printing parameters.
2. Understanding the technology supporting the print and digital work.
3. Insight on how to create Headlines.

Course Outcomes

CO1 Learners will apply editing and proofing of stories.

CO2. Learn the importance of technology supporting the print and digital media.

CO3. Prove using the new software PageMaker.

Course Content

MODULE I

8HRS

Nature, process, and importance.

News room setup,

Role and functions of an editor, news editor, sub-editor. Guest editor.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion / Presentation.

MODULE II

8HRS

Headline, Functions and types of headlines

Techniques of writing headlines

Trends in headline writing.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion / Presentation.

MODULE III

8HRS

Editorial page, Editorials

Types of editorial, Middles

Letters to the editor Op-ed–(opposite to editorial Page)

Articles, advertorials.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion / Presentation.

MODULE IV

8HRS

Techniques of page layout, Latest trends in page layout

Dummy, Pagination, style sheets.

Page making software, PageMaker

Quark Express, In Design -photo editing.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion / Presentation.

MODULE V

8HRS

Editing for radio and television

Rewriting, Translation

Types and techniques of translation.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion / Presentation.

Reference

Brooks, S & Pinson, James L. (2017). *The art of editing in the age of 39onvergence*. NewWork: Routledge.

Ludwig, Mark D. & Gilmore, Gene. (2005). *Modern news editing*: Iowa: Blackwell.

Ross F.Collins (2013). *Editing Across Media: Content and Process for Print andOnlinePublication*. McFarland & Co. Inc

Shrivastava, K.M. (2015). *News reporting and editing*. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers.Prasad, Sharada. (1993). *Editors on editing*. New Delhi: National Book Trust.

Ravindran, R.K. (1999). *Handbook of reporting and editing*. New Delhi: Anmol Publications. Roy, Barun. (2000). *Beginners' guide to journalism*. Delhi: Pustak Mahal.

Sharma, S. (2006). *Editing, Theory and Practice*. New Delhi: Anmol Publications Pvt Ltd.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 2**

21BAJ012: Radio Broadcasting

Subject Code	21BAJ12	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To make students aware of the importance of Radio Broadcasting in India.
2. To educate the basic terms and concepts of Broadcasting.
3. To apply the skill in Radio writing, News drama script and Dramatic Structure.

Course Outcomes

CO1. To give an overview of the structure and functioning of the broadcast industry.

CO2. importance of Radio broadcasting and expected to act in a professional manner.

CO3. Modify the Promos and advertisement in Radio.

Course Content

MODULE I

8HRS

World Broadcast models, Types of Radio programs.

AM, FM, DAB,

Community Radio, Educational Broadcasting,

FM Stations, Private Radio stations.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE II

8HRS

Reporting for radio, Research for Radio News

Radio news Editing, Radio news features

Sound Recording, Studio based Programs

AIR, Podcasting Techniques

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE III

8HRS

Introduction to script writing

Importance of a Script, Various elements of a script

Story- plot- characters, Styles of radio writing

News drama script, Dramatic Structure

Narrative structure, Linear and Non-Linear Techniques of Narrative

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE IV

8HRS

Radio policy, Radio drama

Audio books, Special Events plans – concepts

Producer, Promos and Show Producers

Sales Team, Celebrity bytes

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE V

8HRS

Spoken word programs

Radio Talks, Features programs

Discussion and Interviews, Musical programs

Vocal and Instrumental, Folk programs

Special audience program, Rural, Youth, Women and children's programs

Public Service programs, Health, Educational and Environment programs

Scientific Program, Interactive/ Phone in program

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

Reference

Dr. H.O Srivastava (2000), Broadcast Journalism, Gyan Publishing House, New Delhi.

H. R. Luthra (1986), Indian Broadcasting, Director, Publications Division, New Delhi.

K Parameswaran (2012), Radio Broadcasting, Authors, Jaipur, New Delhi.

P C Chatterji (1991), Broadcasting in India, Sage Publications, New Delhi.

S C Bhatt (1993), Broadcast Journalism, Har Anand Publications, New Delhi.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 2**

21BAJ13 (A) HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Subject Code	21BAJ13(A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To enable the students to understand the HR Management and system at various levels in general and in certain specific industries or organizations.
2. It helps the students to focus on and analyze the issues and strategies required to select and develop manpower resources.
3. To understand the job analysis, recruitment and placement process.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will Summaries the practice of HR Management and system at various levels.

CO2. They are able to relate the general and in certain specific industries or organizations.

CO3. They are able to analyse the issues and strategies required to select and develop manpower resources.

Course Content

MODULE - I

8 HRS

Introduction to Human Resource Management

Definition, Meaning of Human Resource Management, Features, Objectives, Scope, Evolution of HRM, Functions –Managerial – Operative, Role of the HR Manager, Qualities of Human Resource Manager.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Job Analysis and Human Resource Planning

Job Analysis –Meaning, Job Description- Job specification, Job Design- Techniques, HRP- Meaning, Definition, Objectives, Importance of HRP, Process of HRP, Steps to make HRP Effective.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Recruitment and Selection

Recruitment – Definition, Meaning, Objectives, Factors affecting Recruitment Sources of Recruitment, Selection – Meaning, Essentials, Scientific Selection Process, Placement, Induction.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Absenteeism and Labour Turnover

Concept of Absenteeism- Meaning, Causes, Effects, Measures to Reduce Absenteeism. Labour Turnover – Meaning, Causes, Effects, Measures to Reduce Labour Turnover.

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE – V

8 HRS

Wage and Administration

Compensation Administration-Meaning, Objectives, Factors Influencing wage and salary levels, Methods of Wage Payment-Time Wage Payment, Piece Wage Payment, Concept of Minimum Wages, Fair Wages and Living Wages, Fringe Benefits

Pedagogy: Lecture, PPT, Case Studies, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

Reference:

- Human Resource Management- Text and Cases: VSP Rao
- A Hand Book of Personnel Management Practice: Dale Yolder
- Fundamentals of Human Resource management- T.N. chabra
- Human Resource Management- L.M. Prasad
- Human Resource Management- K.S. Ashwathappa
- Personnel management- C.B.Mamoria
- Personnel and Human Resources Management- P Subba Rao

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 2

21BAJ13 (B) YOUTH DEVELOPMENT THROUGH SOCIAL WORK

Subject Code	21BAJ13(B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Understand the concept and perspective of Youth;
2. Knowledge about the status of youth;
3. The approaches, techniques and models of youth work

Course Outcome

CO1.To apply the concept and perspective of Youth

CO2. Discover about the status of youth, the approaches, techniques and models of youth work

CO3.Assess the strategies by which youth development could be achieved.

Course Content

MODULE – I

8 HRS

Understanding Youth

Defining Youth - Social Construction of Youth –Changing conceptions of Youth. Youth Demographics.

Theories on Adolescence: Hall’s storm and stress model, Blo’s theory of Process of Disengagement by adolescents, Richard Jessor’s Problem behavior theory.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE - II

Challenges and Opportunities for Youth

Youth power: youth as social capital - youth as change agents – youth in socio-political movements. Youth in the context of globalization.

8 HRS

Education and Skill Development, Employability and Employment.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE - III

Positive Youth Development

Positive Youth Development: Conceptual Understanding of Positive Youth Development (Competence, Character, Confidence, Connection and Caring). **8 HRS**

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE – IV

8 HRS

Youth Development

Youth Led Development: Concept - Youth Led Sustainable Development in the focus areas of Education and Skill development, Gender equality and Women empowerment, Peace and Non-violence and Climate

Community engagement framework for youth development - Factors promoting and hindering youth engagement in the Community.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE – V

8 HRS

Approaches and Models of Youth Work

Nature and definition of Youth Work.

Approaches to Youth Work – Relief based approach, Welfare based approach, Development based approach and Policy Development based approach.

Models of Youth work – Treatment model, Reform model, Advocacy model, Conscientization model.

Pedagogy: PPT, Quiz, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

John Cotterell (2007), Social Networks in Youth and Adolescence, Routledge, London.

Jones Gill, (2009), Youth, Polity Press, UK.

Kehily Jane Mary (Etd.) (2007), Understanding Youth: Perspectives, Identities and Practices, Sage Publication, London.

Landis H. Paul, (2011), Adolescence and Youth: The Process of Maturing, Sarup Book Publishers Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.

M Sarumathi and Kalesh (2007), Youth Policies and Programmes in South Asia Region, RGNIYD Publication, Sriperumbudur.

Rajendran Vasanthi & Paul David (2006), Youth and Globalisation, Proceedings of the Workshop on Youth and Globalisation, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, Sriperumbudur and Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai.

Sibereisen K. and Richard M. Lerner. 2007. Approaches to Positive Youth Development. Sage Publications. New Delhi.

Verma.M.L. (2010) Youth and Revolutionary Upsurge, Sarup Book Publishers Pvt.Ltd., New Delhi.

Wood Jason and Hine Jean (2009), Theory and Policy for Practice, Sage Publications New Delhi.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 2**

21BAJ24 – Field Practicum – II

Subject Code	21BAJ24	IA Marks	-
Total Contact Hours	16 Hours per week (25 Field work Visits)	Summative Assessment Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	--	Total = 100 Marks	100
Credits	04		

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation.

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to clarify the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to discover skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions.

CO3. Able to assess programmes and projects of governmental and nongovernmental organization

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of Second Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent field work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunity of working with communities, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunity to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

Workload : *Ratio of Teachers and Students for Social Work practicum shall be 1:8*

*Note: * In concurrent Field Work Programme, every student has to undergo 16 hours of Field Work Practicum per week. Two hours of Field Work Practicum is carried out by the students is equated to one hour of theory classes conducted in the Community/ Agency / Institution setting (16 hours of Field Work i.e. two hours = 1 hour theory class). (16/2 = 8 Hrs. the work load for the Field work practicum shall be considered as 1: 8 The Ratio of one teacher shall has a batch of 8 students) (Each teacher has to spend 1 hour per student. i.e. 8 students = 8 hours per week). As per UGC Model Curriculum for Social Work Education [2001, p. 14].*

References

Kumar,S. (2002), Methods for Community Participation: A Complete Guide for Practitioners. London : ITDG Publishing.

Narayana Rao, S. (2002). Counseling and Guidance. Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd O'Hagan,

Tata Institute of Social Sciences (1998) Field Work Manual for First Year Social Work, Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai

Digital References

IGNOU School of Social Work (2013), Field Work Practicum in Social Work Part, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a6u_YBsoKCs

The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda (2019), https://www.msubaroda.ac.in/asset/storage/admission/FSW_Prospectus_2019.pdf

Course Outcome based Curriculum Framework (LOCF) for Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) (2019), https://www.ugc.ac.in/pdfnews/1366718_Social_Work.pdf

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 2**

21BAJ15 -FUNDAMENTALS OF COMMUNICATION II

Subject Code	21BAJ15	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To develop the basic reading and writing skills of first year engineering and technology students.
2. To help learners develop their listening skills, which will, enable them listen to lectures and comprehend them by asking questions; seeking clarifications.
3. To help learners develop their speaking skills and speak fluently in real contexts.

Course Outcome

CO1. Identify the basic principles of communication

CO2. Analyse the various types of communication

CO3. Make use of the essential principles of communication and Identify the prominent methods and models of Communication

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Basics of Communication I

Communication - definition – meaning – elements - basics of communication -

Communication process - importance of communication - the seven C's of communication

Completeness - conciseness – consideration – concreteness – clarity courtesy and correctness.

Barriers to communication - sender-centric – receiver-centric and organizational – socio-Cultural - information overload - overcoming communication barriers.

Practical's: Story framing and narrating (students are asked to frame a story on given topic and narrate it in front of the class)

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Basics of Communication II

Channels of communication - formal and informal – verbal non – verbal - body language -

Sign language -para language circumstantial language - intrapersonal and interpersonal

Communication - group and mass communication - network communication - impact of IT on Communication - pathways of communication - downward – upward - horizontal.

Practical's: Dialogue writing for the given situation (pick a topic on spot and form dialogues and present it like conversation between two people)

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Poetry

Rabindranath Tagore – Leaving this Chanting

William Wordsworth - The World is Too Much with Us

Practical's: Critically analysing the poem. (Analyse the poem in different persons point of view).

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE – IV

Comprehension and free writing

Reading – comprehension-pre-reading-post reading- comprehension questions (multiple choice questions and /or short questions/ open-ended questions)-inductive reading- short narratives and descriptions from newspapers including dialogues and conversations

paragraph writing- free writing, short narrative descriptions using some suggested vocabulary and structures -prepositions, conjunctions Vocabulary development- guessing meanings of words in context.

Practical's: Reading a text and narrating (read any text from magazine, newspaper, comics etc...and summarise it and narrate).

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -V

8 HRS

Grammar and language development

Understanding text structure use of reference words and discourse markers-coherence-

Jumbled sentences Listening – listening to longer texts and filling up the table- product

Description- narratives from different sources. Speaking- asking about routine actions and

Expressing opinions. Language development- degrees of comparison- pronouns- direct vs

Indirect questions- Vocabulary development – single word substitutes- adverbs.

Practical's: Advertising a product (form the students in group, give a product ask them to create a advertisement to that product).

Pedagogy: Lecture, Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

1. Fisk, J. Introduction to Communicative Studies, 1990. London: Routledge.
2. Aggarwal, Shalini. Essential Communication Skills, 2009. New Delhi: Anne Books.
3. Richards, C. Jack. Interchange Students' Book-2 New Delhi: CUP, 2015

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication) SEMESTER 2

21BAJ16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ16 K	Kannada II
21BAJ16 H	Hindi II
21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II
21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BAJ16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 2**

21BAJ17 -Digital Proficiency -II

Subject Code	21BAJ17	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

MODULE –I

4HRS

Browser settings for a secure connection

Working with the operating system: Navigation of the file system using a mouse and keyboard.

Word processing: create a text document; create a letter, report, and greeting card.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –II

4HRS

Create a text document with figures in it. It should describe a concept taught in another course.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –III

4HRS

Discuss the following in a text document about the basic organisation of a computer:

CPU, memory, input/output devices, hard disk.

Create a text document in an Indian language other than English.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –IV

4HRS

Create a presentation.

Create a presentation with animation.

Include existing images/ pictures in a presentation.

Pedagogy: Hands on training, lab and practical sessions

MODULE –V

4 HRS

Animate pictures and text with sound effects in a presentation

Create a simple spreadsheet and perform the following operations: min, max, sum, and average.

Create different types of charts using a spreadsheet: line, bar, area and pie

Pedagogy: Lecture, and Lab/ Practical sessions.

References

Laurelet.al., (2019), Teaching Social Work with Digital Technology, CSWE Press

Godfred Boahen (2020), *COVID-19: Using Digital Technology in Relationship-Based Practice to Bridge the Gap in Social Distancing*, Social care institute for excellence, <https://www.scie.org.uk/social-work/digital-capabilities/blogs/covid-digital-technology>

John Hughes (2020), *Zoom vs Microsoft Teams vs Google Meet: Top Video Conferencing Apps Compared*, codinwp, <https://www.codeinwp.com/blog/zoom-vs-microsoft-teams-vs-google-meet/>

Frederic G. (2019), Social Work Education in a Digital World: Technology Standards for Education and Practice, *Journal of Social Work Education*, 55(2):1-13.

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication) SEMESTER 2

21BAJ18 –Value based NSS Activities

Course Title	NSS Activities	Course Credits	Mode of Delivery
Total Contact Hours	20 Hours Practical	2	Campus Networking Based
Formative Assessment Marks	50 Internal Assessment		

Practical based.

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication) SEMESTER 2

(Online SWAYAM platform)

21BAJ19 –LIFE SKILLS

Subject Code	21BAJ19	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. Learn each other's names and qualities And facilitate communication among students
2. Help participants make new friends, and Make rules for the group
3. Identify and clarify expectations during the training, Develop a sense of trust so that personal growth takes place and Understand how some statements can hurt others

Course Outcome

CO1. CO1. Interpret Self-awareness, interpersonal relationships and communication.

CO2. Discover Self-awareness, critical thinking and communication

CO3. Assess the skills of Empathy, communication and critical thinking

Course Content

MODULE –I

Getting Started to know each other **4HRS**

Mistaken identities, mime an interest, if you were an animal, Celebrities, Find out, Double wheel. Making ground rules, our expectations.

Only positive strokes allowed, Trust me, Catch me quick, Circle of trust, Secret admirer, Lifeboat.

I Love Myself, My “Protective Shield”, I am Happy to be a Girl/Boy.

Pedagogy: Activity Based, Learning by doing, role play and Poster making

MODULE –II 4HRS

My Life Auction, and Values Voting. My River of Life

Act and Meet, Listening, More Listening Skills, Mixed Messages and Choosing Whom to Talk to.

Status and Power, The Chaser, Our Behavior –Passive, Aggressive or Assertive, I and You: Using “I Feel” Statements

Saying “No” and Meaning it (includes persuasion).

Pedagogy: Activity Based, Learning by doing, role play and Poster making

MODULE –III

Communication and Relationships **5HRS**

Relationship Map, The Many Meanings of Love, Obstacle Race, My Best Friend, Wanted: Friends Forever, Abuse: Hurting Someone, Hotline, My Family and Me, I Belong to a Community.

Who is right? Who is wrong? Conflict Ladder, Different Perspectives: This and That, Responses to Conflict. Decision Making, Three Cs in Decision-making, Making Ripples: Good and Bad Decisions, Delaying sex, Best Response, What Should I do?

Pedagogy: Activity Based, Learning by doing, role play and Poster making

MODULE –IV

Problems and Solutions, Excuses, Excuses, You are in the Driver’s Seat, Open Door, and Closed Door, Coping with Emotions and Growing Up, A Book of Me, Happy Memories, A Story of Hope and Big Book, How Different Are We?, How is My Body Changing?

Pedagogy: Activity Based, Learning by doing, role play and Poster making.

MODULE –V

Substance Use and HIV children- Your Choice of Drugs, Even a Little is Too Much, **4 HRS**

Advertisements Do Not Lie, and The Circle of Hurt

The Immune System Dance, HIV Transmission: Doors of Entry, Stop, Go, Think, Am I at

Risk? and STI Quiz

Goals I Can Reach, How Do I Set My Goals?, A “Mantra” for Trying, and Being Responsible.

Pedagogy: Activity Based, Learning by doing, role play and Poster making

Reference

Spaargaren, G., and B. VanVliet. 2000. ‘Lifestyle, Consumption and the Environment: The Ecological Modernisation of Domestic Consumption.’ Environmental Politics. 9(1): 50-75.

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency; Backyard Composting: It's Only Natural; October 2009

Delors, Jacques (1997). Learning: The Treasure Within, UNESCO, Paris.

Nair.V. Rajasenan, (2010). Life Skills, Personality and Leadership, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, Tamil Nadu. Page 8 of 62

UNESCO (2005). Quality Education and Life Skills: Darkar Goals, UNESCO, Paris.

WHO (1999). Partners in Life Skills Education: Conclusions from a MODULE ed Nations Inter-Agency Meeting, WHO, Geneva.

Nair. A. Radhakrishnan, (2010). Life Skills Training for Positive Behaviour, Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development, Tamil Nadu.

Santrock W. John (2006). Educational Psychology. (2nd Edn.) New Delhi: Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Ltd.

Life Skills Resource Manual, Schools Total Health Program, (2006). Health Education and Promotion International Inc., Chennai.

Kumar. J. Keval, (2008). Mass Communication in India, JAICO Publication India Pvt. Ltd

21BSW20 COMMUNICATIVE KANNADA-II

Course Title	Communicative Kannada	Course Credits	0	Mode of Delivery
Total Contact Hours	20 Hours	Non-Credit based	-	Online mode

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
THIRD SEMESTER

21BAJ21 PRINT JOURNALISM

Subject Code	21BSW21	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To create an interest in reading newspapers and magazines.
2. To give insight on the history of newspapers and magazines.
3. To develop the journalism skills in reading and writing in Kannada newspapers.

Course Outcomes

CO1. Learners will inculcate the habit of reading newspaper and Magazine.

CO2. Learners will take part in writing for newspapers and to improve their journalism skills.

CO3. Asses the news processing skills.

Course Content

MODULE 1

8 HRS

Printing in India, New Techniques in Printing;

Types of Printing; Letter Press,

Lithography, Intaglio/Gravure,

Serigraphy, Photo Composition.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE II

8 HRS

Contribution of James Augustus Hickey

James Silk Buckingham, Raja Rammohan Roy.

The first war of Indian independence and the Press.

Freedom struggle and the Press:

B G Tilak, Ghosh brothers, S. Sadanand,

Mahatma Gandhi.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE III

8 HRS

Dainik Bhaskar, Dainik Jagran,

Hindusthan Dainik, The Times of India,

The Hindustan Times, The Statesman, The Hindu, Indian Express,

Udayvani, Vijayavani, Prajavani, Samyuktha Karnataka, Maliyalam Manorama.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE IV

8 HRS

Hermann Moegling, M Venkatakrishnaiah,

T T Sharma, Mohare Hanumantha Rao,

DV Gundappa. Major Kannada Dailies: Samyukta Karnataka,

Prajavani, Kannada Prabha, Udayavani,

Vijaya Karnataka. Tabloids in Kannada.

The present status of Kannada Journalism.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE V

8 HRS

Open, Save and Close Word Document

Editing Text, Tools, Formatting, Bullets

Spell Checker

Navigating in Word; Keyword, Mouse, Document Formatting; Paragraph Alignment, Indentation

Headers and Footers, Numbering, Printing, Preview Options

Templates and Wizards, Table and Contents and Indexes, Tables and Columns.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

Reference

Jeffrey, Robin. (2003). *India's newspaper revolution: Capitalism, politics and the Indian-language Press*, New Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Kumar, J Keval. (2003). *Mass communication in India*. Delhi: Jaico Publishing House.
Murthy, Nadiga Krishna. (1966). *Indian journalism*. Mysore: Prasaranga, Mysore University.

Natarajan, J. (2017). *History of Indian journalism*. New Delhi: Publications Division, Govt. of India:

Parthasarathy, Rangaswami. (2001). *Journalism in India* (4th Ed). New Delhi: Sterling Publishers

RNI (Annual) *Press in India*. Government of India. Available at rni.nic.in

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3

21BAJ22 Advertisement

Subject Code	21BSW22	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. understand the concepts of guidance and counselling
2. understand testing and non-testing techniques in guidance service
3. understand the types of counseling and qualities of an effective counselor.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will be able to explain the meaning of Guidance, Describe the nature of Guidance and

CO2. Discover the scope of Guidance, explain the structure, purpose of guidance, describe goals of guidance and explain principles of guidance.

CO3. Able to create need of guidance with reference to India.

Course Content

MODULE - I

8HRS

Guidance- Meaning, Nature and Scope

Guidance: Goals and Principles, Need for Guidance with Reference to India

MODULE -II

8HRS

Guidance Services

Concept and Importance; Services: Placement Service, Follow up service.

MODULE -III

8HRS

Educational and Vocational Guidance

Organizing Guidance Services at School and College Level

Personal and Group Guidance: Concept, Aims and Methods, Personal Guidance at School Level and Personal Guidance at College Level

MODULE -IV

8HRS

Counseling and Types

Concept, Need and Goals with Reference to India, Counseling: Principles and Counseling Process

Types of Counseling: Directive Counseling, Non-Directive Counseling, Eclectic Counseling, Interview Process in Counseling.

MODULE -V

8HRS

Counseling Services

Individual Counseling, Group Counseling

Organizing Counseling Services at School Level, Organizing Counseling Services at College Level. Problems of Guidance and Counseling.

Psychotherapy: Meaning and Process, Dealing with Psychological Disturbance, Psychotherapy: Cognitive Approach, Environmental Approach ; Counselor: Role and Qualities 10 Testing and Non-Testing Techniques: Psychological Tests, Case Study, Rating Scale, Observation, Interview, Inventories.

Reference

Dr. Kulwinder Pal. Guidance and Counseling. DEDU502 Edited USI PUBLICATIONS 2/31, Nehru Enclave, Kalkaji Ext., New Delhi-110019 for Lovely Professional University Phagwara.

D'Mello Laveena (2018). Therapeutic Counseling Intervention, Srinivas Publication, Mangalore, Karnataka. India. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1314178>

Gail Wilson (2010). Understanding Old Age – Critical and Global Perspectives, *London School of Economics and Political Science*, London, 2010.

Ferreira Monica (1995). A Model for the health care management of older people, unpublished paper read at *an International Conference: Dynamic Ageing - The Challenge*, Cape Town, 4-6.

Jeyalakshmi S. Additional Director General, Chakrabarti S., Deputy Director General Gupta Nivedita Gupta Director, Situation Analysis of the Elderly in India.

Hazan Haim, Old Age Constructions and Deconstructions, ISBN: 9780511621925, Cambridge University Press, 2012.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3**

21BAJ23 (A) DISASTER MANAGEMENT

Subject Code	21BAJ23 (A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To understand key concepts and typologies of disasters
2. To understand Processes of disaster mitigation and disaster management
3. To develop Skills and promote intervention strategies to assess the vulnerability and prepare modules for the future eventualities
4. To develop capacity to work with different agencies at international, national and local levels

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to agree the impact of hazards and disaster.

CO2. Able to respond in vulnerable situation.

CO3. Invent strategies to emergency management to restore the quality of life.

Course content

MODULE I

Introduction to Disasters

8HRS

Disaster: Concept, Meaning, and Definition

History of Major Disaster Events in India

Types of Disasters – Natural Disasters: Famine, Drought, Flood, Cyclone, Tsunami, Earthquake

Man-made Disasters: Riots, Blasts, Industrial, Militancy

MODULE II

Disaster Mitigation and Disaster Management

8HRS

Profile, Forms and Reduction of Vulnerability

Disaster Mitigation: Concept and Principles

Disaster Management: Concept and Principles

Pre-disaster- Prevention and Preparedness

MODULE III

Impact of Disaster **8HRS**

Physical, Economic, Social, Psycho-socio Aspects, Environmental Impacts

During Disaster- Rescue and Relief

Post-disaster- Rehabilitation and Reconstruction

Victims of Disaster- Children, Elderly, and Women

MODULE IV

Disaster Process and Intervention **8HRS**

Displacement- Causes, Effects and Impact

Major Issues and Dynamics in the Administration of Rescue, Relief, Reconstruction and Rehabilitation

Components of Rescue, Relief, Reconstruction; Rehabilitation

Disaster Policy in India; Disaster Management Authority- NDMA, SDMA, DDMA; Disaster Management Act, 2005

MODULE -V

Role of various agencies **8HRS**

1.Role of Government organizations, voluntary organizations, local groups.

2. Community participation, volunteers and social workers.

Reference

Disaster Management, by Harsh K. Gupta

Disaster Management, written by M. M. Sulphey

Disaster Management, written by Vinod K. Sharma

Natural Hazards and Disaster Management, by R. B. Singh

Disaster Management: A Reader, written by S. Rajagopal

Introduction to Emergency Management, written by Bullock Jane, Daman P. Coppola, and George D. Haddow.

Disaster Science And Management, written by Tushar Bhattacharya

Introduction to Disaster Management, written by Satish Modh

Disaster Management, written by I. Sundar

Disaster Management, written by Dr Mrinalini Pandey

Disaster Management: Future Challenges and Opportunities, written by Jagbir Singh

Disaster management, written by J. P. Singhal

Earth and Atmospheric Disaster Management: Nature and Man-made, written by C. K.

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3

21BAJ23 (B) MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM

Subject Code	21BAJ23 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. This Provides the knowledge of contemporary issues related to the field of managing information systems.
2. Develop knowledge and skills required to work effectively in a profession.
3. Enhance self-confidence, ability to make proper decisions and effective communication.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students able to Demonstrate knowledge of contemporary issues related to the field of managing information systems.

CO2. Able to distinguish knowledge and skills required to work effectively.

CO3. Able to adapt self-confidence make proper decisions

Content of Course

MODULE I

8 HRS

The Meaning and Role of MIS

Meaning of MIS? Decision support systems, systems approach, the systems view of business, MIS Organization within the company.

Management Organizational theory and the systems approach: Development of organization theory, management and organizational behaviour.

MODULE II

8 HRS

Database Management

Manager Should Know about Computer Systems: Data processing and the computer, Operation of a manual Information System, Components of a computer system, Conversion of manual to computer-based system.

Database Management: The business settings, Objects of DBMS, Database Technical overview.

MODULE III

8 HRS

Information Systems for Decision Making

Evolution of an information system, Basic Information Systems, decision making and MIS, MIS as a technique for making programmed decisions, decision assisting informationsystems.

Strategic and project planning for MIS: General business planning, appropriate MIS response

MODULE IV

8 HRS

Conceptual System Design

Define the problems, set system objectives, establish system constraints, determine information needs, determine information sources, develop alternative conceptual designs and select one, document the system concept.

MODULE V

8 HRS

Implementation, Evaluation and Maintenance of the MIS

Plan the implementation, acquire floor space and plan space layouts, organize for implementation, develop procedures for implementation, train and operating personnel, computer related acquisitions, develop forms for data collection and information, dissemination, develop the files, test the system, cut over, document the system, evaluate the MIS, control and maintain the system.

Reference

Information Systems for Modern Management- R. G. Murdick, J. E. Ross and J. R. Clagget.

Management Information System: Strategy & Action- Parker, Charles Case, Thomas

Management Information Systems - O' Brien James A

Management Information Systems - Sadagopan S

Management Information Systems - Murdic and Ross

Systems Analysis for Business - Optner

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3**

21BAJ24–Field Practicum III

Subject Code	21BAJ24	IA Marks	100
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	---	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to compare the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to Analyze skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions

CO3. Able to determine programmes and projects of governmental and nongovernmental organization

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of third Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent filed work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunities y of working with communit, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunities y to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3**

21BAJ25 FUNCTIONAL ENGLISH- I

Subject Code	21BAJ25	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Total shift in pedagogy from lectures-oriented classes to interactive learning
2. To familiarize students with the function of grammatical items used to spoken /written language
3. To train students to use the language with confidence & without committing errors

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will heighten their awareness of correct usage of English grammar in writing and speaking.

CO2. They will improve their speaking ability in English both in terms of fluency and comprehensibility in their performance.

CO3. They will give oral presentations and receive feedback on their performance.

Course Content

MODULE –I

8 HRS

Basics of phonetics.

Listening to texts, listening to CDs, Trials of a good listener.

Pronunciation Introduction to English phonetic Symbols consonants & Vowels with illustrations in use.

Listening & Comprehension Interpretation of texts based on question-answer. Interaction among students.

Reading Skill Techniques of reading. Reading comprehension of unseen pages
Identifying the context & the central idea. Vocabulary & word formation from different texts & dictionary

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Creative writings- Basic Grammar Prescriptive/descriptive approaches grammaticality acceptability –appropriateness-grammar in context grammar in spoken & written Practice.

Exercise on the use of different grammatical constructions in context.

Identification of the use of the above given grammatical devices form different texts like newspapers, poems, stories etc.

Words & phrases used for conversation Making statements, questions, order & suggestions – denying –rejecting-disagreeing-possibility-ability, permission, obligations etc.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE -III

8 HRS

Public Speaking, Public speech. Dialogues, Telephonic Conversation, Interview etiquette. (Mock interviews, and documentation).

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation.

MODULE – IV

Communicating Through Technology and Employment Communication.

Introduction- Classification of Technological Tools for Communication

8 HRS

Major Technological tools- Effective Use of Technology for Communication

Communicating Through social media, Communicating in Virtual Teams. Employment Process. Setting Goals- Understanding Employers ‘Mindset towards the Employment Process Organizing Your Approach to the Employment Process. Drafting Résumés and Other Employment Messages. Drafting Application Letters- Handling Group Discussions

Handling Interviews- Drafting Post-Interview Employment Messages

Pedagogy: Practical, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

MODULE -V

8 HRS

Basics of Functional English- An Introduction of the Structures in English Language

Types and Construction of Sentences. Usage of Parts of Speech and Linkers, Usage of Idioms and Phrases for Standardizing Communication, Accent and Pronunciation for Effective Communication.

Explicit Comprehensive Exercises, Implicit Comprehensive Exercises. Converting Titles into meaningful passages.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and presentation

Reference

Fisk, J. Introduction to Communicative Studies, 1990. London: Routledge.

Aggarwal, Shalini. Essential Communication Skills, 2009. New Delhi: Anne Books.

Richards, C. Jack. Interchange Students’ Book-2 New Delhi: CUP, 2015

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSAJ26 K	Kannada III
21BAJ26 H	Hindi III
21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III
21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BAJ26	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3

21BAJ27 CYBER CRIME AND SECURITY

Subject Code	21BAJ27	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To make understand theEvery organization is responsible for ensuring Cyber Security.
2. The ability to protect its information systems from impairment or even theft is essential to success.
3. Implementing effective security measures will not only offer liability protection; it will also increase efficiency and productivity.

Course outcome

CO1.Examinethe different types of malware and security breaches and develop effective prevention methods which will increase overall security.

CO2. Make use of the basic concepts associated with Cyber Security.

CO3. Design measure to safeguard the information.

Course Content

MODULE - I

4HRS

Introduction to Cyber Crime and law.

Cyber Crimes, Types of Cybercrime

Hacking, Attack vectors, Cyberspace and Criminal Behaviour

Clarification of Terms.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

MODULE - II

4 HRS

Traditional Problems Associated with Computer Crime

Understanding the Threat from Cyber Crime Introduction Cyber Threat

Definition of Cyber Crime Classification.

Current Threats and Trends, Diversity of Cyber Crime

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

MODULE – III

Cyber Hate Crimes – Cyber Terrorism.

Responding To Cyber Crime

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

4HRS

MODULE – IV

4HRS

Cyber Strategy, National Security Strategy, Cyber Security Strategy, Organized Crime Strategy

Cyber Crime Strategy, Policy Cyber Crime, International Response, National Cyber Security Structure.

Strategic Policy Requirements, Police and Crime Commissioners.

MODULE – V

4 HRS

Get Safe Online, Cyber Security Guidance for Business, Cyber Crime Investigation Skills, Criminal Investigation

Code of Ethics, Evidence – Hi-Tech Investigations, Capturing and Analysing Digital Evidence.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Assignments and video Clippings.

Reference

Thomas Halt, Adam M. Bossler and Kathryn C. Seigfried Spellar, —Cybercrime and Digital Forensics: An Introduction, Routledge Taylor and Francis Group 2017.

Bernadette H Schell, Clemens Martin, —Cybercrime, ABC – CLIO Inc, California, 2004

Cyber Security: Understanding Cyber Crimes, Computer Forensics and Legal Perspectives, Nina Godbole and Sunil Belapure, Wiley INDIA.

Cyber Security Essentials, James Graham, Richard Howard and Ryan Otson, CRC Press.

Introduction to Cyber Security, Chwan-Hwa(john) Wu, J. David Irwin, CRC Press T&F Group.

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication) SEMESTER 3

21BAJ28 Games

Subject Code	21BAJ28	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Participation in the interested games, Campus based)

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3

21BAJ29 Waste Management

	21BAJ	IA Marks	50
Subject Code	29	Exam Marks	-
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Total Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Exam Hours	-
Credits	02		

Course Objectives

1. To make them understand the Municipal Solid Waste Management.
2. To know the Characteristics, Health and Environmental Effects.
3. To Give insight on Waste Management.

Course Outcome

CO1. Make use of the Practical experience in Solid waste Management.

CO2. To Assess Waste Disposal techniques.

CO3. To build awareness in the community

Course Content

MODULE –I

4 HRS

Municipal Solid Waste Management, Municipal Solid Waste Management.
Generation and Characteristics of Waste. Health and Environmental Effects.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, visit to plant.

MODULE -II

4 HRS

Waste Collection, Storage and Transport, Waste Collection, Storage and Transport.

Record Keeping, Control, Inventory and Monitoring

Implementing Collection and Transfer System.

Case Study-Waste Storage, Collection and Transport

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, visit to plant.

MODULE -III**4 HRS**

Waste Disposal, Waste Disposal - Key issues and features.

Sanitary Landfill. Waste Processing Techniques.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Practical sessions.

MODULE -IV**4 HRS**

Chemical reduction techniques, Volume, size and Chemical reduction techniques.

Source Reduction, Product Recovery and Recycling. Planning of a Recycling Programme. Recycling Programme Elements.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Practical sessions.

MODULE -V**4 HRS**

Composts and Biogas, Recovery of Biological Conversion Products: Composts and Biogas. Composting and Bio gasification: Technology.

Environmental Effects of Composting and Bio gasification. Incineration and Energy Recovery. Hazardous Waste: Management and Treatment.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and group discussions, Practical visits.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 3**

21BAJ30 Communicative Kannada

21BSW30 Communicative Kannada (Spoken Kannada)		
Number of Theory Credits	Number of lecture hours/Semester	Mode of Delivery
Non Credit based	-	Blended mode

SEMESTER 4

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

21BAJ31: Electronic Journalism

Subject Code	21BAJ31	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To course intends to teach Audio - Video production techniques.
2. To understand Digital Journalism.
3. To apply Process of scripting: idea formation.

Course Outcomes

- CO1.** Learner will able to Analyze the Audio - Video production techniques.
- CO2.** Able to apply TV, Cinema and Digital Journalism.
- CO3.** Improve the Script writing and recognize the power of mass media.

Course Content

MODULE I

8HRS

Introduction to Digital Journalism,
Digital Newsroom, News Portals & Their Presentations,
Major Electronic Media Houses,
News Agencies

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE II

8HRS

Script meaning and types of script, Role of a script writer in media,
Elements of good script, Concept of content and form.
Importance of General Knowledge in TV
Process of scripting: idea formation
Research to TV programs.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE III

8HRS

Television, Evolution of Doordarshan.
National and regional programmes, Emergence of satellite
Cable TV channels

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

8HRS

MODULE IV

Types of television channels, news, entertainment, sports, education, children and business channels.

Growth of Kannada television channels.

News and entertainment channels in Kannada.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

8HRS

MODULE V

Evolution of cinema.

Development of cinema in India.

Development of cinema in Karnataka

Popular and new wave cinema, Status of Indian cinema

FTII, NFAI.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

Reference

Bhatt, S.C. (2007). *Broadcast journalism: Basic principles*. New Delhi: Har-Anand.

Chatterji, Shoma A (2014) *100 Years of jump-cuts and fade-outs Tracking change in Indian cinema*. New Delhi: Rupa Publ

Chatterji, P C. (1991). *Broadcasting In India*, 2nd Edition. New Delhi: Sage

Publications. Dijk, Jan van. (2006). *The network society: Social aspects of new media*. New Delhi: Sage.

Saran R (2012) *History of Indian cinema*. New Delhi: Diamod Pocket Books.

Sari, Anil. (2011). *Indian cinema: The faces behind the masks*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.

Shrivastava, K M. (2005). *Broadcast journalism: in the 21st century*. New Delhi

Sterling. Usharani, N. (2006). *Educational Television in India*. New Delhi: Discovery

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4**

21BAJ32: New Media Technology

Subject Code	21BAJ32	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To explore basic concepts of new media.
2. To analyze the role digital media (aka “new media”) technologies play in society.
3. To make them to understand the forms of New Media, Web Journalism, Journalists and the Internet.

Course Outcomes

CO1. Students will make use of digital media technology throughout the course

CO2. Simplify the new media concepts with practical experience.

CO3. Learners able to develop content for internet Medium

Course Content

MODULE – I

8HRS

Introduction to New Media Technology.

Emergence of New Communication Technologies.

Characteristics, Global Village

Globalization, Satellite Television.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE – II

8HRS

Applications of ICT, ARPANET, Internet

Search Engines, Web Radio and TV.

Technological Convergence, ICT and Information Society

Factors Influencing Information Society, Theories of Information Society

Knowledge Society, WSIS Summit on Information Society.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE – III

8HRS

Issues in New Media Technology, Electronic Governance.
Information Super-Highway, Leaf Frogging, Digital Divide.
ICT Grass–Roots Initiatives, New Technology Innovations.
Case Studies.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE – IV

8HRS

Forms of New Media: Web Journalism, Journalists and the Internet.
Electronic Publishing, Virtual Reality.
Information Technology Act 2000.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE – V

8HRS

Content Developing for Internet Medium.
Web – Designing, Web Page, HTTP, HTML.
Software Applications; Photoshop.
MSWindows Application, Page Maker, In-Design.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

Reference

AMIC: Public Service Broadcasting in Asia

Denis Macquill: Mass Communication Theory

F.E. Davis, J.A Barry - L.W. Hall: Newsletter Publishing with Page Maker.

Rogers Cadenhead: Front Page.

Orbicom: New Partnership in Communications for the 21st Century: Orbicom.

Rick Altman: Quark Express for Windows

Chetan Srivastava: Introduction to Information Technology

Santhosh Choubey, Ramprasad: An Introduction to Information Technology and
Computer Fundamental.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4**

21BAJ33 (A) Social Work Research (SWR)

Subject Code	21BAJ33 (A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To introduce social work research methods to social workers.
2. To teach them various methods, types of research.
3. Introduce scientific research data collection methods.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will able to practice the social Work research method.

CO2. They will Examine the statistics and able to use in the research.

CO3. Able to Assess the method of preparing project report.

Course Content

MODULE -I

Research-Meaning and Nature.

8 HRS

Nature and Characteristics, Social Science Research and Social Work Research

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -II

Scientific Methods.

8 HRS

Methods of Research: Historical, Pure and Applied Research, Observation, Survey Method, Case Study and PRA Techniques.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

MODULE -III

Research Design

8 HRS

Exploratory, Descriptive, Experimental, Diagnostic Research Designs. Steps in Research: Selection of Topic, Formulation of Problem, Identification of Variables – Hypothesis.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -IV

Sampling Methods.

8 HRS

Types and Problems of Sampling – Tools of Research: Observation, Questionnaire and Interview Schedule. Research Analysis: Sources of Data, Data Collection, Classification, Tabulation, Analysis and Interpretation.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE -V

Statistical Methods.

8 HRS

Research Report Preparation.

Averages, Dispersions, Correlation.

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion

References

“Research Methodology in Social Science Research” by Sadhu Singh, Himalayan Publishing house, New Delhi.

Research Methodology – A Hand Book by R.P.Misra Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi.

Methods and Technique of Social Survey and Research, by Dr. Vatsayayan, Kedar Nath Ram Nath.

Easthope, Gary, History of Social Research Methods, London, Longman, 1974. 10. Bajpai.

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4

21BAJ33 (B) E- Business

Subject Code	21BAJ33 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. Presents concepts and skills for the strategic use of e-commerce and related information technology from business to consumers.
2. the strategic use of e-commerce and related information technology from business-to-business.
3. Use of e-commerce and related information technology from intra- organization.

Course Outcome

CO1. Students will able to Develop the concepts and skills for the strategic use of e-commerce.

CO2. Related information technology from three perspectives: business to consumers, business-to-business.

CO3. Able to Conclude the concept e business and business to business and intra – organisation.

Course Content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

E-Business Framework. Definition, Origin, History of Internet, Working of E-Business, Advantages and Disadvantages

E- Business v/s Traditional Business Mechanism, E-Business opportunities for Business, Goal of E- Business

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - II

8 HRS

E-Business Technology and Infrastructure, Economic Theories of E-Business, Business -to-consumer (B2C) systems and strategies, Business- to- Business (B2B) models and strategies.

Implication of E-Business strategies, Business Applications: Consumer-oriented and Business-oriented E-Business.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - III

8 HRS

E-Business Payments, Introduction to Electronic Payment Systems (EPS), Types of E-Payments: Credit Cards, Smart cards, E-Cash/ Cyber cash

E-cheque, Micro Payment Systems, Characteristics of Electronic Payment systems, Need of EPS System.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - IV

8 HRS

Internet Environment of E-Commerce

Introduction, E-Commerce Security Environment, Security concerns, Types of security vulnerabilities in E-Business

Internet Economy Conceptual Framework, Providers and Vendors of E-Business Software.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE - V

8 HRS

E-Commerce in India

State of e-business in India, problems and opportunities in e-commerce in India,

Legal issues and Challenges in Indian Perspective, Role of e- business in India

Scope and future of e-business, Impact of e-business on market and retailers and its social impact.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

E Business R(Evolution) - Daniel Amor, Pearson Edude.

E-Commerce Management – Krishnamurthy

E-Commerce: Strategy, Technologies and Applications - David Whiteley

E-Commerce: A managerial Perspectives - P. T. Joseph

The Complete E- Commerce Book - Jance Reynolds

Beginning Ruby on Rails: E- Commerce - JarkkoLaine.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4**

21BAJ34–Field Practicum IV

Subject Code	21BAJ34	IA Marks	100
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	---	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation.

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to compare the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to Analyze skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions

CO3. Able to determine programmes and projects.

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of fourth Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent filed work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunities y of working with communit, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunities y to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4**

21BAJ35 FUNCTIONAL ENGLISH- II

Subject Code	21BAJ35	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To enhance the student's communication skills by giving adequate exposure in listening, speaking, reading and writing skills and the related sub-skills.
2. The course is a step towards preparing the learners to face situations with confidence
3. Able to seek employment in the modern globalized world.

Course Outcome

CO1.Students will heighten their awareness of correct usage of English grammar in writing and speaking.

CO2.They will influence in speaking ability in English both in terms of fluency and comprehensibility in their performance.

CO3.They will defend oral presentations and receive feedback on their performance.

Course Content

MODULE -I

8 HRS

Technical English, Survey Report Writing, meaning of survey, importance of survey, types or 4 basic surveys, structure of a basic survey, presentation and conclusion.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Copy Editing, Scope and needs, Various types of scripts, Qualities and duties of a copy writer, Steps of copy editing, Interaction with the author

Title and cover description- Main features, Incorporating illustrations.

Copy rights, Dealing with Multi authorship, In house manuals. Proof reading and editing.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE -III**8 HRS**

Travel Writings, Scope of the writings, role on creative writing, Writing Travelogues.

Writing Travel-Diaries, Writing Blogs on Tourist Attractions etc.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE – IV**8 HRS**

Review Writing, Review of TV Shows, Style, Presentation and Technique

Book Review, Film Review Music Review

Review of Any Event.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

MODULE- V**8 HRS**

Literature Review

Introduction or background information section; the body of the review containing the discussion of sources; and, finally, a conclusion.

Literature review of the poem Ozymandias by P.B Shelly.

Pedagogy: Individual and Group Discussion, Assignment, and Presentation.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4****21BAJ36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE**

21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV
21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV
21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV
21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BAJ36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

(Attached at the end)

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4**

21BAJ37 ENTREPRENEURSHIP START UP

Subject Code	21BAJ37	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To know the interest in the students to start entrepreneurship.
2. To give basic skills required to start entrepreneurship.
3. To share practical knowledge about entrepreneurship

Course outcome

CO1. Identify the interest in the students to start entrepreneurship.

CO2. To build basic skills required to start entrepreneurship.

CO3. To measure the practical knowledge about entrepreneurship

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and site visits.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4**

21BAJ38 YOGA

Subject Code	21BAJ38	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To introduce Yoga and its brief development.
2. To know principles and classifications of Yoga.
3. To teach some Asanas.

Course outcome

CO1.Students will inculcate the practice of Yoga

CO2.They discuss the important of Yoga and the health benefits of Yoga.

CO3.And also motivate and teach others about Yoga.

Course Content

MODULE -I

4 HRS

Origin of Yoga & its brief development. Meaning of Yoga & its importance

Yoga as a Science of Art (Yoga Philosophy). Meaning of meditation and its types and principles.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -II

4 HRS

Classification of Yoga/Types of Yoga. Hatha Yoga, Raja Yoga, Laya Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Gyan Yoga, Karma Yoga. Asthang Yoga.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -III

4 HRS

Principles of Yogic Practices. Meaning of Asana, its types and principles.

Meaning of Pranayama, its types and principles. Meaning of Kriya its types and principles.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -IV

4 HRS

Yogic therapies and modern concept of Yoga. Naturopathy, Hydrotherapy, Electrotherapy,

Acupressure, acupuncture. Meaning and importance of prayer.

Different mudras during prayers.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

MODULE -V

4 HRS

Effect of Asanas on various Systems. Difference between Asana and Exercise.

Difference between Pranayama and deep breathing. Yogic Diet.

Pedagogy: Practical exposure, Visits, Video clipping and Lecture.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4**

21BAJ39 INDIAN CONSTITUTION & ENVIRONMENTAL STUDIES

Subject Code	21BAJ39	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	2	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Lecture Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

Course Objectives

1. To Enable the student to understand the importance of constitution
2. To understand the structure of executive, legislature and judiciary.
3. To aware about the environmental issues.

Course outcome

CO1. Students were able to Interpret the Indian constitution and its structure of executive, legislature and judiciary.

CO2. They were able to address the issues related to environmental Issues.

CO3. Defend the Constitution.

Course Content

MODULE -I

8 HRS

Introduction to the Constitution of India, Nature of the Indian Constitution, Significance of the Indian Constitution, The Making of the Constitution and Salient features of the Constitution, Preamble of the Indian Constitution, Citizenship

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions.

MODULE -II

8 HRS

Fundamental Rights- Right to Equality, Right to Freedom, Protection of Life and Personal Liberty, right against Exploitation, Right to Freedom of Religion, Cultural and educational rights and right to Constitutional Remedies. Directive Principles of State Policy & Fundamental Duties, Union Executives – President, Prime Minister and Parliament, State Executives – Governor Chief Minister and State Legislature.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

MODULE -III

8 HRS

The Union Judiciary-The supreme court of India, The State Judiciary-The High Court of States. Election Commission of India. The Emergency Provisions and the Amendment of the Constitution.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

MODULE -IV**8 HRS**

Environmental Studies- Introduction, Definition, Nature, Scope and Importance. Eco System- Concept, Structure, Functions and Components of Eco System. Natural Resources- Forest, Water, Mineral, Food, Energy and Land Resources.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

MODULE -V**8 HRS**

Environmental Pollution- Meaning, Definition, Causes, Types: Air Pollution, Water Pollution, Soil Pollution, Marine Pollution, Thermal Pollution and Nuclear hazards. Environmental Issues: Climate Change, Global Warming, Acid Rain, Ozone Layer depletion, Nuclear Accident, Bopal Gas Leakage tragedy and Population Explosion. Legal measures- Environmental Protection Act, Constitutional Provisions and Judicial Remedies.

Pedagogy: Lecture, individual and Group discussions, and Brainstorming sessions

Reference

- Indian Constitution - D Dbasu
Constitutional Law of India - J.N. Pandey
Constitution law of India - M. P. Jain
The Constitution of India - Dr.ParvathyAppaiha
Environmental Law and Policy in India - Shyam Divan and Armin Rosencranz
Environment and Ecology - MajidHussain

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 4****21BAJ40 Communicative Kannada**

21BSW40 Communicative Kannada		
Number of Theory Credits	Number of lecture hours/Semester	Mode of Delivery
Non-Credit based	-	Online mode

SEMESTER 5

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

21BAJ41: Public Relation

Subject Code	21BAJ41	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To intends to expose students with the creative and management aspects of Public Relations.
2. To includes planning and execution of Public Relations campaigns.
3. Apply the steps in planning and organization.

Course Outcomes

CO1. Learners will able to practice the creative and management aspects of Public Relations.

CO2. Students able to plan and execute the Public Relations.

CO3. Understand the problems of PR in relation to media and explain all the steps of planning and organizing an event

Course Content

MODULE I

8HRS

Public Relations – definition – nature

Scope and functions – origin and development of Public Relations in India.

Public Relations Process – fact finding, planning, implementation and evaluation

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE II

8HRS

Differences among advertising

Publicity, propaganda

Public opinion

Responsibilities of a Public Relations practitioner

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE III

8HRS

Tools of Public Relations – print, radio, film, television

New media, Photography

House journals, Exhibitions

Open House

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE IV

8 HRS

The need for event- Cooperative communication,

Social cause, Image development,

Event and Public, Event and marketing,

Event creativity, Event management,

Strategic marketing planning, Events and media planning management

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Group Discussion/Presentation and Practical

MODULE V

8 HRS

Problems and prospects of Public Relations

Event management

Code of ethics in Public Relations

Professional organizations: PRSI-PRCI – IPRA

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

Reference

Bhimani, Rita. (2018). PR2020: The trending practice of public relations.

New Delhi: BEE Books. Reddy, C.V. Narasiman. (2014). *Effective public relations and media strategy* (92nd edition). Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.

Sachdeva.S.Iqbal. (2009). *Public Relations: Principles and Practices*. New Delhi: Oxford University Express.

Sardana, C.K. (2000) *Applied public relations in the Indian context*. New Delhi: Harananda Publicaitons.

Scott, David Meerman. (2010). *The new rules of marketing and PR*. Hoboken

John Wiley & Sons c. Singh J.K. (2007). *Media and public relations*. NewDelhi: Kul Bhushan Nangia APH

Smith. D. Ronald. (2009). *Strategic planning for public Relations*. New York: Routledge.

Solis, Brain & Brackenridge, Deirdre. (2009). *Putting the Public Back inPublic Relations*. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Education

Sharma, Diwakar; Event Planning and Management, Regal Publications

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ42: Film Production

Subject Code	21BAJ42	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To deal with various aspects of cinema in technical and analytical terms including history, relevance and role in society and perceptions among the masses.
2. To learn Voice recording in Cinema.
3. To teach the importance of cinematic medium.

Course Outcomes

CO1. Students will be able to apply the complete process of cinema making.

CO2. Assess the greatest films and makers of all times.

CO3. Create a Documentary movie.

MODULE I

8HRS

Brief history of cinema,

Lumiere brothers, attempt to capture moving images,

Cinematographe, the era of silent movies

Early films in Europe

History of Indian Cinema

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE II

8HRS

Aspects of Cinema

Talkies, voice recording for cinema

George Millis's Trip to the Moon

Dziga Vertov's Man with a Moving Camera

Special effects in early cinema

Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE III

8HRS

Camera Movement, script

Screen play and montage

The importance of cinematic medium
Great masters of world cinema
Alternate and parallel cinema
Further Theory, Feminist film Theory, Formalist film theory
Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE IV

8HRS

Introduction to Documentary films
History of documentaries
Grammar of Documentary films
Examples of Documentary
Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

MODULE V

8HRS

Digitalization in Cinema
Digital technology in Cinema, concepts of digital editing
Digital correction of colors
Manipulations
Possible opportunities and limitations
Pedagogy: Lecture, Assignment, Individual and Group Discussion/Presentation.

Reference

- Baudry, Leo & Marshall, Cohen (Eds) (1999) *Film Theory and Criticism*-5thed, New York: Oxford University Press.
- Nichols, Bill (Eds)(1993) *Movies and Method*. Vol.1&2. Calcutta, Seagull Books.
- Giannetti, Louis(1993) *Understanding Movies*, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Gledhill, Christen & Williams, Linda, *Reinventing Film Studies*, London; Arnold Publishers.
- Nelmes, Jill (1996) *An Introduction to Film Studies*, New York: Routledge

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ43 (A) HEALTH CARE

Subject Code	21BAJ43 (A)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. To develop an understanding of the Holistic concept of Health.
2. To have understanding of the health situation in India.
3. To develop an understanding about mental disorders and to promote healthy life style.

Course Outcome

CO1.To extend the functions of management and administration of the healthcare

CO2.To Classify healthcare delivery systems.

CO3. To integrate healthcare ethics

Course Content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

Definition, Dimensions of Health, Determinants of Health

Indicators of Health. Mental Health - Warning signals of poor mental health, Causes of mental health problems.

Types of mental illness

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- II

8 HRS

First aid during emergency- contents of the first aid box

First Objects in the ear, nose, eye, Bleeding from nose and bleeding due to other injuries

Bites- snake bite, dog bite, insect bite, Burns, Electric shock, lightning

Fainting, epilepsy, Poisoning - food poisoning

Suffocation – drowning, choking, Fractures, fall and bandages

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- III

8 HRS

Introduction to the systems of medicine – Ayurveda, Allopathy, Homeopathy
Naturopathy and Unani.

Female Health Problems and Home Remedies/Management:

Guidelines for Pregnant Women

Guidelines for Women after Delivery

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- IV

8 HRS

Stress: Definition, Causes of Stress. Physical signals of Stress, Effects of Stress, Simple Ways to Manage Stress

Obesity: Causes for Obesity, Managing Obesity, Cholesterol Management,

Cancer- Causes of Cancer, Prevention and Control

Heart attack: Causes and Prevention, Diabetes Mellitus- Causes, Prevention and Care.

Blood Pressure (BP) & Acidity, Causes, Prevention and Care

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- V

8 HRS

Concept of health care. Levels of Health Care

Principles of Health Care. Health system in India-The central, State, District and Village level

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

Centre for Environment Education. The Green Action Guide. 2nd ed. Ministry of Human Resource Development, Govt. of India, 2006.

Improve your Mental Health and Efficiency. Bangalore: Navakarnataka Publications Pvt. Ltd., 2010.

Chandrashekar, C.R. Mind your Mind. Bangalore: Navakarnataka Publications Pvt. Ltd., 2010.

Goel, Rajnesh. Community Health Care. New Delhi: Deep and Deep Publications, 2008.

Goel, S.L. Health Care Administration: Levels and Aspects. Bangalore: Sterling Publishers Pvt. Ltd., Bangalore, 1984.

Government of India. India Year Book 2014. New Delhi: Ministry of Information and Broadcasting, 2014.

Gulani, K.K. Community Health Nursing: Principles and Practices. New Delhi: Kumar Publishing House, 2009.

Jayaraman, Rukmani. Give Them Facts: Help Them Decide. Chennai: TT Rangahathan Clinical Research Foundation, 2000.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ43 (B) ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT

Subject Code	21BAJ43 (B)	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. The objective of entrepreneurial development is to motivate a person for entrepreneurial career.
2. Make capable of perceiving and exploiting successfully opportunities for enterprises.
3. To analyze the role of Entrepreneurship in Indian and the economic development with reference to Self-employment development.

Course Outcome

CO1. Learners will able to apply Entrepreneurship's skills.

CO2. Able to examine the project.

CO3. Able to criticize the role of Government in motivating the Entrepreneurship.

Course Content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

Meaning-Concept of Entrepreneurship, History of Entrepreneurship Development.

Role of Entrepreneurship in Indian economic development with reference to Self-employment development.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Development, Attributes and Characteristics of successful Entrepreneur.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- II

Business Idea-Method of generating idea and opportunities recognition

8 HRS

Preparing Business Plan- Meaning, Significance of Business Plan

Components of Business Plan, Business Planning Process

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- III

8 HRS

Technical -Financial- Marketing, Personnel and Management Feasibility

Estimating Financing Funds requirements

Functions and Schemes offered by various commercial banks and financial institutions

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- IV

8 HRS

Role of Central Government and State Government in promoting Entrepreneurship.

Introduction to various incentives, Subsidies and Grants Export Oriented MODULE s

Role of following agencies in the EntrepreneurshipDevelopment.

District Industries Centers, Small Industries.

Service Industries. Entrepreneurship Development of India.

National Institute of Entrepreneurship and small business development.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- V

8 HRS

Role of Entrepreneurship Qualities of Successful Entrepreneurs

Risk faced by the Present Entrepreneur, Reasons for Low/ No Entrepreneurs

Women Entrepreneurs: Role, Problems, Prospects, Social entrepreneurship- Concepts - Importance- Barriers inEntrepreneurship.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

- | | |
|---|---|
| Entrepreneurial Development | -Vasanth Desai |
| Small and Medium Enterprises in India | -Indian Institute ofBanking and Finance |
| Essentials of Business Environment & Entrepreneurship | -Aswathappa K |
| Support System for Entrepreneurs | - Moulik T.K |
| Government as Entrepreneur | - Albert. N |

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ44 Field Practicum V

Subject Code	21BAJ44	IA Marks	100
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	---	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. To understand the basics of fieldwork, concept of self and fieldwork and the professional role of social workers.
2. To critically understand and appreciate programmes and projects of governmental and non-governmental organizations.
3. To enhance importance of skills in report writing and documentation

Course Outcome

CO1. Able to compare the concept of field work education to develop self-awareness.

CO2. Able to Analyze skills in field work report writing, record of the observation visits and engage in meaningful discussions during group interactions

CO3. Able to determine programmes and projects.

Course Content

Field Work Contents (Tasks/Activities)

Field work practicum of Second Semester comprises Concurrent field work

Concurrent Field Work: The broad aim of concurrent field work practicum is to provide opportunities for applying the knowledge and the information gained in the classroom to reality situations. This learning experience should provide an opportunity of working with community, groups, individuals/families and managing organization tasks. It is an opportunity to develop intervention skills in reality situations. This entails learning social work practice for two days (16 hours) in every week of the semester.

The student shall complete a minimum of 26 days of visits in a semester. The learners shall be placed in agencies/community to initiate and participate in direct service delivery. Submission of reports to their allotted respective faculty supervisors.

The faculty supervisors through periodic Individual conferences and Group conferences shall assist students to prepare a plan of action for the respective semester fieldwork activities in consultation with agency supervisors.

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ45 PUBLIC RELATION

Subject Code	21BAJ45	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	04	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Course Objectives

1. This course intends to expose students with the creative and management aspects of Public Relations.
2. The course includes planning and execution of Public Relations campaigns.
3. To know the tools and advertising Public Relations.

Course Outcome

CO1. Learners will able to clarify the concept Public Relations.

CO2. Able to discover the tools of public relation

CO3. Able to decide and manage the events.

Course content

MODULE- I

8 HRS

Public relations – definition – nature, scope and functions

Origin and development of Public Relations in India.

Public Relations Process – fact finding, planning, implementation and evaluation.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- II

8 HRS

Differences among advertising, Publicity

Propaganda, Public opinion

Responsibilities of a Public Relations practitioner

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- III

8 HRS

Tools of Public Relations

Print, Radio, Film, Television

New media, Photography, House journals, Exhibitions, Open House.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- IV

8 HRS

Types of Public Relations. Government, private, public sector

Community relations. Employee relations, media relations

Public Relations in democracy.

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

MODULE- V

8 HRS

Problems and prospects of Public Relations.

Event management, Code of ethics in Public Relations

Professional organizations: PRSI-PRCI – IPRA

Pedagogy: Brainstorming, Assignment, Presentation, Individual and Group Discussion.

Reference

Bhimani, Rita. (2018). PR2020: The trending practice of public relations.

New Delhi: BEE Books. Reddy, C.V. Narasiman. (2014). *Effective public relations and media strategy* (92nd edition). Delhi: PHI Learning Private Limited.

Sachdeva.S.Iqbal. (2009). *Public Relations: Principles and Practices*. New Delhi: Oxford University Express.

Sardana, C.K. (2000) *Applied public relations in the Indian context*. New Delhi: Harananda Publicaitons.

John Wiley & Sons c. Singh J.K. (2007). *Media and public relations*. NewDelhi: Kul Bhushan Nangia APH.

Smith. D. Ronald. (2009). *Strategic planning for public Relations*. New York:Routledge.

Solis, Brain & Brackenridge, Deirdre. (2009). *Putting the Public Back inPublic Relations*. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Education

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ46 EXCEL AND SPSS

(Online Mode)

Subject Code	21BAJ46	IA Marks	
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	
Total Number of Lecture Hours	-	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	--

Course Objectives

1. This course intends to expose students Excel and SPSS software.
2. The course includes online Platform – SWAYAM.
3. To use tools SPSS in the research.

Course Outcome

CO1. Learners will able to practice EXCEL software.

CO2. Able to do Charts, correlation using SPSS.

CO3. Able to Create data entry of their research by using software.

Course content

(SWAYAM flat form)

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ47 CASE STUDY ON NGO

Subject Code	21BAJ47	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Practical Session on case studies and develop as publishable paper)

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ48 MUSIC/DANCE

Subject Code	21BJ48	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Participation in the interested music and dance. Campus based)

**Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)
SEMESTER 5**

21BAJ49 Street Play

Subject Code	21BAJ49	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	-	Exam Marks	-
Total Number of Practical Hours	20	Total Marks	50
Credits	02	Exam Hours	-

(Participation in the interested Street Play with relevant theme, Campus based)

SEMESTER 6

Bachelor of Arts (BA Journalism and Mass Communication)

21BAJ51 Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce

Subject Code	21BAJ51	<u>IA Marks</u> Internal Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300	300 Marks
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	--	Exam Marks External Assessment Field practicum + Project 150 +150 = 300 Viva-Voce exam = 150	450 Marks
Total Number of Hours Internship & Dissertation to produce a News Magazine & Viva-Voce	320		750 Marks
Credits	28	Total Marks Exam Hours	-

First semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW06 K/ 21BAJ06 K	Kannada I
21BSW06 H/ 21BAJ06 H	Hindi I
21BSW06 M/ 21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I
21BSW06 O/ 21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BSW06/ 21BAJ06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ಪದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

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| ೧. ಕುರುರಾಜಂ ಮಾನಹಾನಿಗೆ ನೊಂದಂ | - ರನ್ನ |
| ೨. ತಿರುಕೊಳವಿನಾಚಿಯ ಪ್ರಲಾಪ | - ಷಡಕ್ಷರದೇವ |
| ೩. ಜೀವಪರ ನಿಲುವಿನ ವಚನಗಳು | - ಬಸವಣ್ಣ |
| ೪. ಮಾದ ಮಾದಿ | - ಬಿ. ಎಂ. ಶ್ರೀ. |
| ೫. ಬರತಿರೇನ ಪಂಥರಪುರಕ | - ಸವದತ್ತಿ ಸಿದ್ದಪ್ಪ |
| ೬. ಹಳ್ಳಿ ಪ್ಯಾಟಿ ಕದನ | - ಮಲ್ಲ ಬಸವ |
| ೭. ತಿಳಿದವರೇ ಹೇಳಿ | - ವೈದೇಹಿ |
| ೮ ಕಟ್ಟಿತೇವ ನಾವು | - ಸತೀಶ ಕುಲಕರ್ಣಿ |
| ೯. ಬುದ್ಧನಿಗೊಂದಿಷ್ಟು ದಾರಿ ಬಿಡಿ | - ಸತ್ಯಾನಂದ ಪಾತ್ರೋಟ |

ಗದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

- | | |
|------------------------------|------------------------|
| ೧೦. ಸುಮತಿ ಕಥೆ | - ಶಿವಕೋಟ್ಯಾಚಾರ್ಯ |
| ೧೧. ಅಡ್ಡ ಹೆಸರು | - ಡಾ. ಎಂ. ಎಂ. ಕಲಬುರ್ಗಿ |
| ೧೨. ಕನ್ನಡ ರಂಗಭೂಮಿ | - ಡಾ. ಬಾಳಣ್ಣ ಸೀಗೆಹಳ್ಳಿ |
| ೧೩. ಸಂತ ಕವಿ ಅಮೀರ್ ಖುಸ್ರೋ | - ಫಕೀರ ಮಹ್ಮದ ಕಟ್ಟಾಡಿ |
| ೧೪. ಹುಳಿಮಾವಿನ ಮರ ಮತ್ತು ನಾನು | - ಇಂದಿರಾ ಲಂಕೇಶ |
| ೧೫. ಹಟ್ಟಿಯಲ್ಲಿ ಹುಟ್ಟಿದ ಕನ್ನಡ | - ಡಾ. ಮೊಗ್ಗಿ ಗಣೇಶ |
| ೧೬. ಭವದ ಬೀಜ ಮೊಳೆವಲ್ಲಿ | - ಚನ್ನಪ್ಪ ಅಂಗಡಿ |

Second semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW16 K/ 21BAJ16 K	Kannada II
21BSW16 H/ 21BAJ16 H	Hindi II
21BSW16 M/ 21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II
21BSW16 O/ 21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BSW16/ 21BAJ16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ಪದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

೧. ಧನ್ವಂತರಿ ಕಥೆ
೨. ವಚನಗಳು
೩. ತನುವ ನೀರೊಳಗದ್ದಿ ಫಲವೇನು?
೪. ಬುದ್ಧ
೫. ನಾಜೂಕದ ನಾರಿ
೬. ಅನ್ವೇಷಣೆ
೭. ಅಗಸ್ತ್ಯ ಹದಿನೈದು
೮. ಹಸಿದ ಹೊಟ್ಟೆಯ ಹಾಡು

- ನಯಸೇನ
- ವಚನಕಾರರು
- ಪುರಂದರದಾಸರು
- ಅಂಬಿಕಾತನಯದತ್ತ
- ಬೆಟಗೇರಿ ಕೃಷ್ಣಶರ್ಮ
- ಜಿ. ಎಸ್. ಶಿವರುದ್ರಪ್ಪ
- ಚಂದ್ರಶೇಖರ ಪಾಟೀಲ
- ಅನಸೂಯಾ ಕಾಂಬಳೆ

ಗದ್ಯ ಭಾಗ

೯. ಗೆಲವು
೧೦. ಪರಿಸರ ಮತ್ತು ಪ್ರಜ್ಞೆ
೧೧. ಶಬರಿಗಾದನು ಅತಿಥಿ ದಾಶರಥಿ
೧೨. ಹೊಸ ದಿಕ್ಕಿನಡೆಗೆ
೧೩. ಕಾಗಿ ಶಕುನ
೧೪. ಸ್ವಾತಂತ್ರ್ಯ ಸಂಗ್ರಾಮದ ಬೆಳ್ಳಿಚುಕ್ಕೆ: ಕಿತ್ತೂರು ರಾಣಿ ಚೆನ್ನಮ್ಮ
೧೫. ಆರ್ತನಾದ
೧೬. ಸರ್ಕಸ್

- ಮಿರ್ಜಿ ಅಣ್ಣಾರಾಯ
- ಡಾ. ಶಿವರಾಮ ಕಾರಂತ
- ದೇ. ಜವರೇಗೌಡ
- ಅಪ್ಪಾರಾಯ ಎಂ. ಮದರಿ
- ಡಾ. ಎಚ್. ಟಿ. ಪೋತೆ
- ಮನು ಬಳಿಗಾರ್
- ಮೂಲ: ಇರಾವತಿ ಕವಕನ್ನಡಕ್ಕೆ:
- ಚಂದ್ರಕಾಂತ ಪೋಕಳೆ
- ಬಸವಣ್ಣಪ್ಪಾ ಕಂಬಾರ

Third semester –Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW26 K/ 21BAJ26 K	Kannada III
21BSW26 H/ 21BAJ26 H	Hindi III
21BSW26 M/ 21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III
21BSW26 O/ 21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BSW26/ 21BAJ26	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ನಿಗದಿತ ಪಾಠಗಳು

ಅಂಕಗಳು: ೨೪

೧. ಉಪರಂಭಿಯ ಪ್ರಸಂಗ - ನಾಗಚಂದ್ರ
೨. ನಾವು ಸಾರಥಿಯಾದೆವು - ಕುಮಾರವ್ಯಾಸ
೩. ವ್ರೀಹಿ -ನರೇಂದ್ರೇಗ ವಾಗ್ವಾದ- ಕನಕದಾಸ
೪. ತರವಲ್ಲ ತಗಿ ನಿನ್ನ ತಂಬೂರಿ - ಶಿಶುನಾಳ ಶರೀಫ
೫. ನಾವೆಲ್ಲರೂ ಒಂದೆ ಜಾತಿ - ಎಂ. ಗೋಪಾಲಕೃಷ್ಣ ಅಡಿಗ
೬. ಕುರಿಗಳು ಸಾರ್ ಕುರಿಗಳು - ಕೆ. ಎಸ್. ನಿಸಾರ್ ಅಹಮದ್
೭. ಎನ್ನ ದೇವರ ಗುಡಿ- ಅಮೃತ ಸೋಮೇಶ್ವರ
೮. ಅಪ್ಪನಿಗೆ ಒಂದು ಪತ್ರ- ಎಚ್. ಗೋವಿಂದಯ್ಯ
೯. ಎರಡು ಭೂರ್ಜ ಪತ್ರಗಳು - ಸ. ಉಷಾ
೧೦. ಲೈನ್‌ಮನ್ ಮಡಿವಾಳ ಭೀಮಪ್ಪನಿಗೆ- ಸತೀಶ ಕುಲಕರ್ಣಿ
೧೧. ಪ್ರಶ್ನೆಗಳಿರುವುದು ಶೇಕ್ಸ್‌ಪಿಯರನಿಗೆ - ಜಿ.ಎನ್. ಮೋಹನ್
೧೨. ಪಾಂಡವರ ಅಜ್ಞಾತವಾಸ- ಜನಪದ

ಪಠ್ಯ ೨ - ಚಂದಳರು (ಪ್ರಬಂಧಗಳು)

ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಡಾ. ಕೆ.ಅಭಯಕುಮಾರ್

ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಪ್ರೊ.ಎನ್.ಭವಾನಿಶಂಕರ ರಾವ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಮೋಹನದಾಸ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಕೇಶವ ಎಚ್.

ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು: ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ, ೨೦೧೦

Fourth semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW36 K/ 21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV
21BSW36 H/ 21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV
21BSW36 M/ 21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV
21BSW36 O/ 21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BSW36/ 21BAJ36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

ನಿಗದಿತ ಪಾಠಗಳು

ಅಂಕಗಳು: ೨೪

೧. ಕನ್ನಡ ಮೌಲ್ಯ - ಗೊರೂರು ರಾಮಸ್ವಾಮಿ ಅಯ್ಯಂಗಾರ್
೨. ಹಳ್ಳಿಗರೊಡನೆ ಸಾಕ್ರಟಿಸ್- ರಂಜಾನ್ ದರ್ಗಾ
೩. ನುಂಗಲಾರದ ತುತ್ತು- ಕೆ.ಪಿ.ಪೂರ್ಣಚಂದ್ರ ತೇಜಸ್ವಿ
೪. ಓಬಾಮ-ನೀನು ಅಮೆರಿಕವನ್ನು ಬದಲಿಸಬಲ್ಲೆಯೆ? - ಡಾ.ಮುಜ್ಜಾಫರ್ ಅಸ್ಸಾದಿ
೫. ಪೂರ್ವದ ಅಪೂರ್ವ ಹಾಂಗ್‌ಕಾಂಗ್- ನಾಗೇಶ್ ಹೆಗ್ಡೆ
೬. ರತ್ನಗರ್ಭಾ ವಸುಂಧರಾ- ನಳಿನಿ ಮೂರ್ತಿ

ಪಠ್ಯ ೩ -ಚಂದಳರು (ಕಥೆಗಳು)

ಪ್ರಧಾನ ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಡಾ. ಕೆ.ಅಭಯ ಕುಮಾರ್
ಸಂಪಾದಕರು: ಪ್ರೊ.ಎನ್.ಭವಾನಿಶಂಕರ ರಾವ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಮೋಹನದಾಸ್, ಶ್ರೀ ಕೇಶವ ಎಚ್.
ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು: ಪ್ರಸಾರಾಂಗ, ಮಂಗಳೂರು ವಿಶ್ವವಿದ್ಯಾನಿಲಯ, ೨೦೧೦

ನಿಗದಿತ ಪಾಠಗಳು

ಅಂಕಗಳು: ೧೬

೧. ಮೋಚಿ - ಭಾರತೀಪ್ರಿಯ
೨. ಅಂಗಡಿ ಪೂಜೆ - ಆರ್. ವಿ.ಭಂಡಾರಿ
೩. ಕಣ್ಣಪ್ಪನ ಅಂತಿಮ ದಿನಗಳು- ಪಿ. ಲಂಕೇಶ್
೪. ಬಿತ್ತಿ ಬೆಳೆದವರು- ಸಾರಾ ಅಬೂಬಕರ್

ಪಠ್ಯ ೪- (ಕಾದಂಬರಿ) ಮಾಧವಿ -ಅನುಪಮ ನಿರಂಜನ

ಅಂಕಗಳು -೧೬

ಪ್ರಕಾಶಕರು: ಡಿ.ವಿ.ಕೆ.ಮೂರ್ತಿ, ಮೈಸೂರು; ೧೯೭೬

First semester – Hindi syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW06/21BAJ06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW06 K/ 21BAJ06 K	Kannada I
21BSW06 H/ 21BAJ06 H	Hindi I
21BSW06 M/ 21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I
21BSW06 O/ 21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BSW06/ 21BAJ06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

I. कालजयी कहानियाँ (कहानी संग्रह)

2x12=24 Hr

- 1) चंद्रधर शर्मा गुलेरी – उसने कहा था
- 2) प्रेमचन्द – कफन
- 3) यशपाल–परदा
- 4) भीष्म साहनी –चीफ की दावत
- 5) उषा प्रियंवदा– वापसी
- 6) जयशंकर प्रसाद – गुण्डा
- 7) फणीश्वरनाथ रेणु – पंचलाइट,
- 8) अज्ञेय – रोज़
- 9) मोहन राकेश – मालवी
- 10) कमलेश्वर – दिल्ली में एक मौत

II कालजयी लघु कथाएँ (लघु कथा संग्रह)

1x12=12 Hr

प्रेमचंद, नासिरा शर्मा, असगर वजाहत, चित्रा मुद्गल, सुकेश साहनी, बलराम, महेश–दर्पण

III. गबन – प्रेमचन्द (उपन्यास)

3x12=36 Hr

Prescribed Books:

- 1) कालजयी कहानियाँ – सं. वी. कुमार, लोकभारती प्रकाशन, इलाहाबाद
- 2) गबन – प्रेमचन्द, जगत भारती प्रकाशन , इलाहाबाद
- 3) कालजयी लघु कथाएँ (लघु कथा संग्रह) सुमित्र प्रकाशन,दिल्ली

Second semester – Hindi Syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW16 K/ 21BAJ16 K	Kannada II
21BSW16 H/ 21BAJ16 H	Hindi II
21BSW16 M/ 21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II
21BSW16 O/ 21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BSW16/ 21BAJ16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

Unit 1 : मध्य कालीन काव्य :

अ 1तुलसीदास -बालकांड, अरण्यकांड, सुंदरकांड, लंका कांड, अयोध्या कांड, अरण्यकांड, किष्किंधा कांड, उत्तरकांड।

आ, 2. मीराबाई की पदावली।

इस, 3. रहीम के दोहे.

Unit 2. आधुनिक काव्य,

अ जयशंकर प्रसाद ,-ले चल वहां भुलावा देकर।

2. सूर्यकांत त्रिपाठी निराला,--बादल राग।

3. नागार्जुन, --मास्टर।

4. केदारनाथ सिम्हा--कमरे का दानव।

Unit 3. कहानियां ।

1. महादेवी वर्मा,--गौरा गाय (रेखाचित्र) .

2. अमरकांत ,-दोपहर का भोजन।

Unit 4. व्याकरण।

1. पत्र लेखन, 2. विज्ञापन, 3. भेंट वार्ता, 4. स्ववृत्त लेखन। (नौकरी और विवाह के लिए)।

5. वाक्य परिवर्तन,--(काल के आधार पर)।

Third semester –Hindi syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW26 K/ 21BAJ26 K	Kannada III
21BSW26 H/ 21BAJ26 H	Hindi III
21BSW26 M/ 21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III
21BSW26 O/ 21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BSW26/ 21BAJ26	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

II. हिन्दी कविता (काव्य संग्रह)

2x12=24 Hr

- 1) कबीरदास – साँच कौ अंग, भेष कौ अंग 2)सूरदास – गोकुल लीला 3) तुलसीदास – दोहावली
- 4) बिहारी – छन्द

II. आधुनिक हिन्दी कविता

2x12=24 Hr

1. मैथिलीशरण गुप्त- मातृभूमि, मनुष्यता, भारत-भारती .2 जयशंकर प्रसाद – बड़े चलो, बीती विभावरी, जाग री – श्रद्धा सर्ग
2. सूर्यकान्त त्रिपाठी निराला – वर दे वीणा वादिनी ,संध्या सुंदरी, राम की शक्ति पूजा
3. सुमित्रानन्दन पंत – मोह, संध्या, गा कोकिल
4. महादेवी वर्मा – वे मुस्कराते फूल, जो तुम आ जाते एक बार
5. रामधारी सिंह दिनकर – हिमालय, अभिनव मनुष्य, चाँद और कवि
6. केदारनाथ अग्रवाल – बसन्ती हवा, धरती, हिन्दी

III. गीत पुंज (गीति काव्य)

2x12=24 Hr

- 1) गोपालदास नीरज – जीवन नहीं मरा करता है 2) ज्ञानवती सक्सेना – जीवन अनुभव पुस्तक
- 3) डॉ. सरिता शर्मा – बेटी 4) बालकवि बैरागी – अपनी गंध नहीं बेचूँगा

Prescribed Books:

- 1) हिंदी कविता- सं डॉ. नामदेव, डॉ. नीलम अक्षर पब्लिशर्स, दिल्ली
- 2) आधुनिक हिन्दी कविता – डॉ. नागरत्ना, डॉ. सुमा टी. आर., वाणी प्रकाशन, दिल्ली
- 3) गीत पुंज – डॉ. विष्णु सरतदे, राजकमल प्रकाशन , दिल्ली

Fourth semester – Kannada syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW36 K/ 21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV
21BSW36 H/ 21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV
21BSW36 M/ 21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV
21BSW36 O/ 21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BSW36/ 21BAJ36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

I. युगे-युगे क्रांति- विष्णु प्रभाकर (नाटक)

2x12=24 Hr

II. एकांकी संगम (एकांकी संग्रह)

2x12=24 Hr

1. रामकुमार वर्मा – घर का मकान
2. जगदीशचन्द्र माथुर – रीढ़ की हड्डी
3. उदयशंकर भट्ट – दस हजार
4. विनोद रस्तोगी – बहू की विदा
5. उपेन्द्रनाथ अश्रक – नए मेहमान,
6. विष्णु प्रभाकर – सीमा रेखा
7. सेठ गोविन्ददास – सच्चा धर्म
8. जि.जे. हरिजीत – आखेट

III नुक्कड नाटक

1. गाँव से शहर तक
2. अपहारण भाईचारे का

2x12=24 Hr

Prescribed Books:

- 1) युगे-युगे क्रांति- विष्णु प्रभाकर, राजपाल और सन्स, दिल्ली
- 2) एकांकी संगम – गणपति भट्ट, डॉ. शिवराम, अमन प्रकाशन, कानपुर
- 3) नुक्कड नाटक- लोक भारती प्रकाशन, दिल्ली

First semester – Malayalam syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ06 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW06 K/ 21BAJ06 K	Kannada I
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21BSW06 H/ 21BAJ06 H	Hindi I
21BSW06 M/ 21BAJ06 M	Malayalam I
21BSW06 O/ 21BAJ06 O	Online Mode I

Subject Code	21BSW06/ 21BAJ06	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

മലയാളം

ലക്ഷ്യങ്ങൾ

- മലയാള ഭാഷയിലെ കഥ, കവിത, നോവൽ, യാത്രവിവരണം, ജീവിച്ചരിത്രം തുടങ്ങിയ സാഹിത്യ ഗണങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള നല്ല ധാരണ കുട്ടികളിൽ വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക.
- സാമാന്യമായ സാഹിത്യ പരിചയവും വായനഭിരുചിയും ആസ്വാദനശേഷിയും വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക
- ഭാഷയുടെ അതിസാന്ദ്രരൂപമായ കവിതയിൽ ആസ്വാദനശേഷി വർദ്ധിപ്പിക്കുക

പഠന ഫലങ്ങൾ

- വിദ്യാർത്ഥികളിൽ വായനാ ശീലം വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു
- സർഗ്ഗർമാക രചനയിലെ സൗന്ദര്യത്മകത വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു
- ഭാഷയുടെയും വിവിധ സംസ്കാരങ്ങളുടെയും വത്തെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള ധാരണ ലഭിക്കുന്നു

യൂണിറ്റ് 1 കവിതകൾ

പൂക്കാതിരിക്കാനെന്നിയ്ക്കാവതില്ലേ - അയ്യപ്പപ്പണിക്കർ
 അങ്ങേ വീട്ടിലേക്ക് - ഇടശ്ശേരി
 സന്ദർശനം - ബാലചന്ദ്രൻ ചുള്ളിക്കാട്

ഒരു പാട്ടു പിന്നെയും - സുഗതകുമാരി

യൂണിറ്റ് 2 ചെറുകഥകൾ

നെയ്പ്പായസം - മാധവിക്കുട്ടി

പ്ലാവില കഞ്ഞി - തകഴി

യൂണിറ്റ് 3 നോവൽ

ഉമ്മാച്ചു - ഉറുബ്

ബാല്യകാല സഖി - ബഷീർ

യൂണിറ്റ് 4 നാടകങ്ങൾ

നാടക ചരിത്രം

ഇന്ദിപ്പസ് - സി ജെ തോമസ്

സ്വപ്ന വാസവദത്തം - വള്ളത്തോൾ

യൂണിറ്റ് ഭാഷ 5 വിചിന്തനം

ഭാഷയും സാഹിത്യവും - എ ശ്രീധര മേനോൻ

ഇംഗ്ലീഷിന്റെ സ്വാധീനം മലയാളത്തിൽ - ഡോ. ജാൻസി ജെയിംസ്

Second semester – Malayalam syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ16 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW16 K/ 21BAJ16 K	Kannada II
21BSW16 H/ 21BAJ16 H	Hindi II
21BSW16 M/ 21BAJ16 M	Malayalam II
21BSW16 O/ 21BAJ16 O	Online Mode II

Subject Code	21BSW16/ 21BAJ16	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

മലയാളം

ലക്ഷ്യങ്ങൾ

- മലയാള ഭാഷയിലെ കഥ, കവിത, നോവൽ, യാത്രവിവരണം, ജീവിച്ചരിത്രം തുടങ്ങിയ സാഹിത്യ ഗണങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള നല്ല ധാരണ കുട്ടികളിൽ വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക.
- സാമാന്യമായ സാഹിത്യ പരിചയവും വായനഭിരുചിയും ആസ്വാദനശേഷിയും വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക
- ഭാഷയുടെ അതിസാന്ദ്രരൂപമായ കവിതയിൽ ആസ്വാദനശേഷി വർദ്ധിപ്പിക്കുക

പഠന ഫലങ്ങൾ

- വിദ്യാർത്ഥികളിൽ വായനാ ശീലം വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു
- സർഗ്ഗർമാക രചനയിലെ സൗന്ദര്യത്മകത വർദ്ധിക്കുന്നു
- ഭാഷയുടെയും വിവിധ സംസ്കാരങ്ങളുടെയും ഉത്ഭവത്തെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള ധാരണ ലഭിക്കുന്നു

യൂണിറ്റ് - 1 കവിതകൾ

- 1) മത്സ്യം - ടി. പി രാജീവൻ
- 2) വാഴക്കുല - ചങ്ങബുഴ
- 3) ചെറിയവ - കുമാരനാശാൻ
- 4) ഇനിയും മരിക്കാത്ത ഭൂമി - ഒ. എൻ. വി

യൂണിറ്റ് - 2 വിവർത്തനം

- 1) വിവർത്തനത്തിലേക്ക് ഒരു ജാലകം
- 2) വിവർത്തനം എന്ത്? എന്തിന്?
- 3) വിവർത്തനത്തിന്റെ പ്രശ്നങ്ങൾ

യൂണിറ്റ് - 3 ചെറുകഥ

- 1) മോതിരം - കാരൂർ
- 2) ഒട്ടകം - എസ്. കെ പൊറ്റക്കാട്
- 3) തിരുത്ത് - എൻ. എസ് മാധവൻ
- 4) പ്രഹരം - കെ. പി രാമുണ്ണി

യൂണിറ്റ് -4 നാടകം

- 1) അടുകളയിൽ നിന്ന് അരങ്ങത്തേക്ക് - വി. ടി ഭദ്രത്തിരിപ്പാട്
- 2) രാവുണ്ണി - എം പി താജ്

യൂണിറ്റ് - 5 നോവൽ

- 1) ശബ്ദങ്ങൾ - ബഷീർ
- 2) കാലം - എം. ടി
- 3) നെല്ല് - വത്സല

Third semester – Malayalam syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ26 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW26 K/ 21BAJ26 K	Kannada III
21BSW26 H/ 21BAJ26 H	Hindi III
21BSW26 M/ 21BAJ26 M	Malayalam III
21BSW26 O/ 21BAJ26 O	Online Mode III

Subject Code	21BSW26/ 21BAJ26	IA Marks	50
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Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

മലയാളം

ലക്ഷ്യങ്ങൾ

- മലയാള ഭാഷയിലെ കഥ, കവിത, നോവൽ, യാത്രവിവരണം, ജീവിച്ചരിത്രം തുടങ്ങിയ സാഹിത്യ ഗണങ്ങളെക്കുറിച്ചുള്ള നല്ല ധാരണ കുട്ടികളിൽ വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക.
- സാമാന്യമായ സാഹിത്യ പരിചയവും വായനഭിരുചിയും ആസ്വാദനശേഷിയും വളർത്തിയെടുക്കുക
- ഭാഷയുടെ അതിസാന്ദ്രരൂപമായ കവിതയിൽ ആസ്വാദനശേഷി വർദ്ധിപ്പിക്കുക

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Fourth semester – Malayalam syllabus

Bachelor of Social Work (BSW) and BA Journalism and Mass communication

21BSW36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BAJ36 –COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE

21BSW36 K/ 21BAJ36 K	Kannada IV
21BSW36 H/ 21BAJ36 H	Hindi IV
21BSW36 M/ 21BAJ36 M	Malayalam IV
21BSW36 O/ 21BAJ36 O	Online Mode IV

Subject Code	21BSW36/ 21BAJ36	IA Marks	50
Number of Lecture Hours/Week	4	Exam Marks	50
Total Number of Lecture Hours	40	Total Marks	100
Credits	03	Exam Hours	2 hrs

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